

MEGARA

DATA REDUCTION COOKBOOK

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Multi
Espectrógrafo en
GTC de
Alta
Resolución para
Astronomía

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The most up-to-date version of this document is available at

<https://guaix-ucm.github.io/megaradrp-cookbook/>

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This webpage is an updated version of the original cookbook (dated 07/07/2020), available in PDF format at this [zenodo link](#). That document was prepared by África Castillo Morales, Sergio Pascual Ramírez and Armando Gil de Paz. As the aforementioned document has become slightly outdated over time, we have decided to move the documentation to this website that allows for easier updates. Nicolás Cardiel López and Mario Chamorro Cazorla have also joined this task.

Important: We strongly recommend using the most up-to-date information available on this [webpage](#).

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope

The goal of this document is to guide any potential user of the MEGARA instrument in its data processing, from the raw data provided by the GTC to wavelength- and flux-calibrated scientific-valid data. The MEGARA data processing described in this document will be done using the MEGARA Data Reduction Pipeline (DRP) which is available through *github* at <https://github.com/guaix-ucm/megaradrp>.

1.2 MEGARA instrument

MEGARA (*Multi-Espectrógrafo en GTC de Alta Resolución para Astronomía*) is a fiber-fed spectrograph with both Integral-Field (IFU) and Multi-Object (MOS) capabilities that was installed and commissioning at the 10.4m GTC telescope in the Spring of 2017. Since semester 2018B, MEGARA is available to the GTC community (Spain, Mexico and UF) in its two modes (LCB and MOS). The reader is referred to Gil de Paz et al. (2020, submitted) for more details.

The MEGARA IFU, which is called Large Compact Bundle (LCB hereafter), covers a field of $12.5 \times 11.3 \text{ arcsec}^2$ using 567 hexagonal spaxels of 0.62 arcsec in size plus 56 sky spaxels of equal size distributed in 8 bundles of 7 fibers distributed in the outskirts of the field at about 2 arcmin from the center of the LCB. The MOS makes use of a set of 92 robotic positioners each hosting a minibundle of 7 spaxels also of 0.62 arcsec in size each spaxel. These can patrol overlapping circular regions of 28 arcsec in diameter. These robotic positioners are distributed in a square region of $3.5 \times 3.5 \text{ arcmin}^2$, which roughly corresponds to the flat and non-vignetted focal plane of GTC at its Folded-Cassegrain F (FC-F) focus (see **Figure 1**). The MOS can be reconfigured starting from a list of target positions in matter of roughly a minute to a few minutes, depending on the level of number of overlapping patrol areas to be explored in a given configuration.

Figure 1: LCB and MOS in the focal plane of MEGARA at the Folded-Cass F focus of GTC. Left: Layout of the monolithic microlens array of the LCB placed at the optical axis of the instrument. Center: Hexagons representing the patrol areas of the 92 robotic positioners of the MEGARA MOS (in light grey) along with the positions of the eight sky bundles that are mounted along the LCB pseudo-slit (in orange). Note that the actual patrol areas are overlapping circular regions of 28 arcsec in diameter, while the distance between adjacent positioners is 24.5 arcsec. Right: MEGARA focal plane before the field lens was installed at the Laboratorio de Instrumentación Científica Avanzada (LICA-UCM) laboratory.

Both the LCB and the MOS along with other subsystems (focal-plane cover, Folded-Cassegrain rotator adapter, etc.) are located at the FC-F focus of GTC. The 623 (567+56) fibers of the LCB and the 644 fibers of the 92 robotic positioners of the MOS are routed through from the FC-F rotator to the Nasmyth A platform following a 44.5m-long path until they reach the MEGARA spectrograph. The MEGARA spectrograph is a fixed-angle (68°) collimator-camera system that is fed by two interchangeable curved pseudo-slits (LCB/MOS). The collimator is an all-refractive F/3 system composed by 5 lenses (1 aspheric singlet and 2 doublets) while the also all-refractive camera is composed by 7 lenses (two doublets, one with a CaF_2 lens, and 3 singlets). In between collimator and camera, the spectrograph pupil can host different types of Volume-Phase Holographic (VPH) disperser elements, namely the low- (LR), mid- (MR), and high-resolution (HR) VPHs. Six LR VPHs cover the entire optical window at $R=6,000$, while 10 MR VPHs provide also full optical coverage but at $R=12,000$. Finally, the two HR VPHs allow observing in the $\text{H}\alpha + [\text{NII}]$ region and in the CaT region with $R=20,000$, although the optical design could in principle accommodate HR VPHs at any other optical wavelength. In **Figure 2** we show the resolving power and spectral coverage for each VPH as measured during the integration and commissioning of the instrument. Note that in some of the cases the spectral coverage shown is shorter than the one actually achieved simply because the spectral lamp lacks bright spectral features (on which to measure the spectral resolution and resolving power), especially at the blue end of the optical spectral range.

Figure 2: Plots showing the relation between resolving power (R_{FWHM}) and wavelength coverage for all 18 MEGARA VPHs and for the LCB (left) and MOS (right) modes. Design values (colored lines) and measurements (grey lines that correspond to individual fiber spectra, while black thick and thin lines represent the mean and mean $\pm 1\sigma$ curves when all fiber spectra are used) are both shown.*

The details on the different VPHs that can be used with MEGARA is given in Table 1. This table also includes the reciprocal (linear) dispersion (CDELTA) and wavelength for the initial pixel (CRVAL for CRPIX=1) as adopted for the MEGARA DRP for different VPHs. The user is referred to different publications to learn more about the MEGARA instrument, including Gil de Paz et al. (2016), Gil de Paz et al. (2018) and Carrasco et al. (2018).

VPH Name	Setup	R_{FWHM}	$\lambda_1\text{-}\lambda_2$ Å	λ_c Å	$\Delta\lambda$ (@ λ_c) Å	Δv km/s	lin res Å/pix	λ (pix 1) Å
VPH405-LR	LR-U	6028	3653 – 4386	4051	0.672	50	0.186	3620
VPH480-LR	LR-B	6059	4332 – 5196	4800	0.792	49	0.23	4280
VPH570-LR	LR-V	6080	5143 – 6164	5695	0.937	49	0.27	5060
VPH675-LR	LR-R	6099	6094 – 7300	6747	1.106	49	0.31	6030
VPH799-LR	LR-I	6110	7220 – 8646	7991	1.308	49	0.37	7140
VPH890-LR	LR-Z	6117	8043 - 9630	8900	1.455	49	0.41	7960
VPH410-MR	MR-U	12602	3917 - 4277	4104	0.326	24	0.089	3905
VPH443-MR	MR-UB	12370	4225 – 4621	4431	0.358	24	0.10	4210
VPH481-MR	MR-B	12178	4586 – 5024	4814	0.395	25	0.11	4568
VPH521-MR	MR-G	12035	4963 – 5443	5213	0.433	25	0.122	4944
VPH567-MR	MR-V	11916	5393 – 5919	5667	0.476	25	0.132	5375
VPH617-MR	MR-VR	11825	5869 – 6447	6170	0.522	25	0.145	5850
VPH656-MR	MR-R	11768	6241 – 6859	6563	0.558	25	0.16	6210
VPH712-MR	MR-RI	11707	6764 – 7437	7115	0.608	26	0.17	6735
VPH777-MR	MR-I	11654	7382 – 8120	7767	0.666	26	0.1845	7360
VPH926-MR	MR-Z	11638	8800 - 9686	9262	0.796	26	0.225	8770
VPH665-HR	HR-R	18700	6445 - 6837	6646	0.355	16	0.0974	6390
VPH863-HR	HR-I	18701	8372 - 8882	8634	0.462	16	0.13	8350

Table 1: MEGARA VPHs: scientific requirements (The resolution, $R_{\text{FWHM}} = \lambda/\Delta\lambda_{\text{FWHM}}$, is derived from the FWHM ($\Delta\lambda_{\text{FWHM}}$) of the 1D spectra). The values of the linear reciprocal dispersion and the wavelength of pixel 1 correspond to the linear solution implemented in the MEGARA DRP after the images are wavelength calibrated.

Note that the reciprocal dispersion is the one used for the linear solution in the images processed by the MEGARA Data Reduction Pipeline.

MEGARA DATA REDUCTION PIPELINE

Figure 3: Data processing scheme of the MEGARA DRP.

The deployment of the MEGARA instrument at GTC was accompanied by the installation of a fully functioning Data Reduction Pipeline (DRP hereafter) developed in Python that worked both online at the telescope and offline. The online version of the DRP allows for on-the-fly data processing, which includes bias correction, trimming, fiber tracing and fixed-aperture extraction, fiber-flat and twilight-flat correction and wavelength calibration. The offline processing (to which this cookbook is devoted) additionally includes a detailed cross-talk-corrected extraction and absolute flux calibration whenever possible. The MEGARA DRP can be obtained through *github* at <https://github.com/guaix-ucm/megaradrp> (section 3). Line lists and the CCD Bad-Pixels Mask (BPM) are available at <https://zenodo.org/record/2270518>.

The MEGARA DRP has been designed to cope with all effects associated to the observation with a fiber-fed spectrograph on which the detection of the light is done with a Charge-Coupled Device (CCD). These effects include the removal of the bias level and the dark current associated to the MEGARA CCD, the tracing and extraction of the flux from each fiber on the CCD, the variation in the wavelength calibration solution along the (pseudo-)slit of the spectrograph and the correction from the variation in sensitivity (from blue-to-red and global) from fiber to fiber and the determination of the system efficiency. In **Figure 3** we show the data processing scheme followed by the MEGARA DRP. We note here that the wavelength calibration is performed quite early on in the reduction procedure as the correction for blue-to-red variation in sensitivity has to be done once the wavelength of the light falling in each pixel and each fiber is known.

The final products of the MEGARA DRP are “reduced” Row-Stacked Spectra (RSS hereafter) 2D images including for 623 (644) fiber spectra for the LCB (MOS) mode, all using a common flux calibration and wavelength solution with constant reciprocal dispersion for all fibers. Based on the averaged spectrum of all fibers to be used for sky subtraction

(by default all 56 sky fibers in the LCB and all unassigned minibundles in the case of the MOS) the DRP also generates a sky-subtracted “final” RSS spectrum. No combo products combining different spectral setups are yet generated.

DRP INSTALLATION

The MEGARA pipeline is a Python package, for Python 3.9 or greater.

The easiest method of installing megaradrp is using `pip` inside a virtual environment. You can install official releases or the development version. All the commands in the following sections, starting with `$` are to be run under **bash shell**.

3.1 Install with pip

A virtual environment creates isolated Python installations, with (potentially) different package versions. We will use the `venv` package (a module in the standard library) here, although the `virtualenv` package can also be used.

The steps to run MEGARA DRP in a virtual environment are:

3.1.1 Create a virtual environment

A virtual environment will have a *name* and a *path*. In order to create a virtual environment called e.g. `megara` using `venv`:

```
$ python3 -m venv megara /path/to/
```

With `virtualenv`:

```
$ virtualenv-3 megara /path/to/
```

The directory `/path/to` represents the location of the environment.

It can be any valid directory path. If the path name is not specified, it will be created in the working directory (notice that virtual environments shouldn't be moved after creation).

3.1.2 Activate the environment

After creating the environment, the directory `/path/to/megara` contains a Python tree. One of the directories is `/path/to/megara/bin`, which contains a script called `activate`. To activate the environment, we source (a bash shell command) this script file:

```
$ source /path/to/megara/bin/activate
```

which yields a different system prompt to the user:

```
(megara) $
```

Now, the name of the environment appears before the standard prompt. We can use the environment only on those consoles / terminals where we have previously activated it.

3.1.3 Install megaradrp with pip

After the activation, we can install megaradrp with pip. This is the standard Python tool for package management. It will download the package and its dependencies, unpack everything and compile when needed.

What follows is a sample of the output:

```
(megara) pip install megaradrp
Collecting megaradrp
Collecting scikit-image (from megaradrp)
Downloading https://files.pythonhosted.org/packages/11/c7/
→ee75c79dcce057a3475763d611ec044737a708eaf5cc53426b0117795ddb/scikit_image-0.14.0-cp35-
→cp35mu-manylinux1_x86_64.whl (25.4MB)
Collecting scipy (from megaradrp)
(...)
Building wheels for collected packages: toolz, scandir
Running setup.py bdist_wheel for toolz ... done
Running setup.py bdist_wheel for scandir ... done
Successfully built toolz scandir
Installing collected packages: decorator, networkx, cloudpickle, numpy,
toolz, dask, six, PyWavelets, python-dateutil, subprocess32, cyclcr,
backports.functools-lru-cache, pytz, pyparsing, kiwisolver, matplotlib,
scipy, pillow, scikit-image, enum34, atomicwrites, more-itertools,
pluggy, attrs, scandir, pathlib2, py, funcsigns, pytest, astropy, PyYaml,
numina, megaradrp
```

3.1.4 Test the installation

Now we can test the installation by running the numina command:

```
(megara) $ numina show-instruments
INFO: Numina simple recipe runner version 0.34
Instrument: MEGARA
  version is '0.16'
  has profile 'Configuration at LICA' uuid=9a86b2b2-3f7d-48ec-8f4f-3780ec967c90
  has profile 'Configuration at GTC' uuid=ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48
  has profile 'Test component' uuid=4fd05b24-2ed9-457b-b563-a3c618bb1d4c
  has profile 'Configuration for the Simulator' uuid=66f2283e-3049-4d4b-8ef1-
→14d62fcb611d
  has datamodel 'megaradrp.datamodel.MegaraDataModel'
  has pipeline 'default', version 1
```

The particular output of the command may change, but Instrument: MEGARA text should always appear.

3.1.5 Update within the environment

In order to update the MEGARA DRP to the latest stable release, the user should execute:

```
(megara) $ pip install -U megaradrp
```

3.1.6 Deactivate the environment

To exit the environment is enough to exit the terminal or run the command deactivate.

```
(megara) $ deactivate  
$
```

3.2 Install in conda

Conda was created with a target similar to virtualenv, but now has extended its functionality to package management for different languages.

You can install [miniconda](#) or [anaconda](#). The difference is that miniconda provides a light-weight environment and anaconda comes with lots of Python packages.

If you have updated the \$PATH variable during install, you can call conda commands directly in the shell, like this:

```
$ conda info
```

If not, you will need to add the path to the command (an example path could be `mini conda3/bin`), like:

```
$ /path/to/conda/bin/conda info
```

If that is the case, you should add that path every time you run a conda command hereafter. Alternatively, you can initialize conda for your own shell by doing:

```
$ conda init bash
```

This works as it is if you are using a login-shell (terminal), but if you are using an xterm, you might also need to do:

```
$ cp ~/.bash_profile ~/.bashrc
```

(do a backup copy of `~/.bashrc` if you have one already),

and open a new terminal/xterm. Below, we will write the commands without the full path, for simplicity. If you are using conda version 4.4+ your terminal will open in the conda (*base*) environment. If you want to avoid that permanently just do: `conda config --set auto_activate_base false`.

Once conda is installed according to the instructions above, the steps to run MEGARA DRP under conda would be the following:

3.2.1 Create a conda environment

We first recommend that you update your conda installation to its latest by doing:

```
(base) $ conda update conda
```

With conda, environments are created in a centralised manner (under directory `./envs` in your conda tree), we do not pass the path to the environment.

```
(base) $ conda create --name megara python=3
```

One could remove this environment (and all its content), if needed, by simply doing:

```
(base) $ conda remove --name megara --all
```

3.2.2 Install megaradrp with conda

Packages can be installed before activating the environment. We provide conda packages for megaradrp in the [conda-forge channel](#)

```
(base) $ conda install --name megara -c conda-forge megaradrp
Fetching package metadata .....
Solving package specifications: .
Package plan for installation in environment /home/xxx/devel/miniconda3/envs/megara:
The following NEW packages will be INSTALLED:
astrophy: 2.0.8-py35_0 conda-forge
atomicwrites: 1.1.5-py35_0 conda-forge
attrs: 18.1.0-py_1 conda-forge
....
zlib: 1.2.11-h470a237_3 conda-forge
Proceed ([y]/n)? y
```

3.2.3 Activate the environment

The functionality is similar to virtualenv:

```
(base) $ conda activate megara
(megara) $
```

Again, after activating the environment, the name of the environment appears before the standard prompt. We can use the environment only on those consoles / terminals where we have previously activated it.

3.2.4 Test the installation

Now we can test the installation by running the numina command:

```
(megara) $ numina show-instruments
INFO: Numina simple recipe runner version 0.34
Instrument: MEGARA
  version is '0.16'
  has profile 'Configuration at LICA' uuid=9a86b2b2-3f7d-48ec-8f4f-3780ec967c90
  has profile 'Configuration at GTC' uuid=ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48
  has profile 'Test component' uuid=4fd05b24-2ed9-457b-b563-a3c618bb1d4c
  has profile 'Configuration for the Simulator' uuid=66f2283e-3049-4d4b-8ef1-
↪14d62fcb611d
  has datamodel 'megaradrp.datamodel.MegaraDataModel'
  has pipeline 'default', version 1
```

3.2.5 Update within the environment

In order to update the MEGARA DRP within the conda environment the user should execute:

```
(megara) $ conda update megaradrp
```

3.2.6 Deactivate the environment

To exit the environment is enough to exit the terminal or run the command source deactivate

```
(megara) $ conda deactivate
(base) $
```

3.2.7 Update outside the environment

Once outside the conda environment one can also update the MEGARA DRP installation by doing:

```
(base) $ conda update megaradrp -n megara
```

If you want to deactivate the conda (*base*) environment entirely you can run again:

```
(base) $ conda deactivate
$
```

3.3 Development version

For those of you interested in installing the development version, please consult the instructions at the readthedocs.org webpage at <https://megaradrp.readthedocs.io/en/latest/installation.html>. The use of the development version is recommended to have access to the latest DRP improvements.

DATA DESCRIPTION

In order to help the user in understanding the different execution steps of the MEGARA DRP, we describe in this section the characteristics of the main products, including input raw images and pipeline products (images and tables).

4.1 Raw Data

Raw data includes all FITS frames delivered to the user by GTC. These FITS images are 4196 x 4212 pixels in size have two extensions, the first one including the data themselves and the second one providing all the information about the fibers (positions in the sky, bundle to which they belong and whether they are devoted to the observation of target or sky). Among these images one can find bias frames (as they are obtained with the **MegaraBiasImage** observing mode they include the name of this mode in their filename), fiber-flat images (obtained with either the **MegaraTraceMap** or the **MegaraFiberFlatImage** observing modes), ThAr or ThNe HCL lamp spectra (obtained with the **MegaraArcCalibration** observing mode) and scientific observations with either the LCB (**MegaraLcbImage** or **MegaraLcbAcquisition**; this latter mode is commonly used when the target is a bright star, normally a spectrophotometric standard star) or the MOS (**MegaraMosImage**).

4.2 Pipeline Products

There are multiple types of products generated by the MEGARA DRP although they can be grouped in full-frame FITS images of 4096 x 4112 pixels in size (after the overscan+prescan regions are removed from the raw images), RSS images of 4300 x 623 (for LCB) or 4300 x 644 (for MOS) pixels, and structured data, which is in most cases are given in files of JSON format. Below we list the different products within these three groups along with the recipe that generates them.

4.2.1 Full-frame FITS image products

- `master_bias.fits` (**MasterBiasImage**): Final image of the MasterBiasImage recipe.
- `reduced_image.fits` (**MegaraDarkImage**, **MasterTraceMap**, **MegaraModelMap**, **MegaraFiberFlatImage**, **MegaraArcCalibration**, **MegaraTwilightFlatImage**, **MegaraLcbStdStar**, **MegaraLcbAcquisition**, **MegaraLcbImage**, **MegaraMosImage**, **MegaraArcCalibration**): Final image after all individual exposures have been processed and combined.
- `master_slitflat.fits` (**MegaraSlitFlat**): Image obtained by observing a continuum-lamp light with the spectrograph out of its optimal focus. The level of de-focusing should be enough to ensure a uniform illumination through the entire CCD but keeping the wavelength of the light approximately the same at each given pixel that when the instrument is well focused.

- `fwhm_image.fits` (**MegaraArcCalibration**): Voronoi map of the FWHM derived from the fits to the Gaussian profiles of all spectral lines identified in the arc-lamp image.

4.2.2 RSS FITS image products

- `master_fiberflat.fits` (**MegaraFiberFlatImage**): Image to be applied to correct for variations in sensitivity in between fibers and from blue-to-red within each fiber.
- `master_twilightflat.fits` (**MegaraTwilightFlatImage**): Image to be applied to correct for the effect of illumination introduced by the fiber-flat image when this was obtained through the FC-F ICM and differences between the pupil of the ICM and the GTC pupil when the object was observed. The values of the twilight-flat image are identical for all wavelengths but different from fiber to fiber (blue-to-red sensitivity variations were corrected with the fiber-flat image).
- `reduced_rss.fits` (**MegaraLcbAcquisition**, **MegaraLcbStdStar**, **MegaraLcbImage**, **MegaraMosImage**, **MegaraArcCalibration**): Processed image prior to the subtraction of the sky spectrum.
- `sky_rss.fits` (**MegaraLcbAcquisition**, **MegaraLcbStdStar**, **MegaraLcbImage**, **MegaraMosImage**, **MegaraArcCalibration**): RSS image showing signal only in the valid sky fibers. All other pixels are set to zero.
- `final_rss.fits` (**MegaraLcbAcquisition**, **MegaraLcbStdStar**, **MegaraLcbImage**, **MegaraMosImage**, **MegaraArcCalibration**): Processed image after the subtraction of the sky spectrum is performed. In the case of the MOS, this image includes an extension of 92 rows by 4300 columns where all 7 fibers of each minibundle have been added together.

4.2.3 Structured products

- `master_wlcalib.json` (**MegaraArcCalibration**): File with the information on the wavelength calibration solution for every fiber.
- `master_traces.json` (**MasterTraceMap**): File with the tracing information.
- `master_model.json` (**MasterModelMap**): File with the information on how to account for the cross-talk between adjacent fibers in the detector.

In the case of the **MegaraLcbStdStar** recipe, the MEGARA DRP also generates two different 1D spectra, that of the standard star obtained after extracting the 37 spaxels around the centroid identified in the observation-result file (`star_spectrum.fits`) and also the resulting sensitivity function (`master_sensitivity.fits`).

In addition to all these files, the results directory of every recipe includes also a file named `task.yaml` (file with the description of the execution of the recipe), the file `result.yaml` (names of the files resulting from the recipe and some quality-control information) and the `processing.log` logging file.

Besides ds9/SAOimage or similar software packages, the FITS products generated by the MEGARA DRP can be also visualized using the tool `numina-ximshow` distributed as part of **numina**.

DATA REDUCTION

5.1 Getting Started

The first step to start the data reduction is to activate your environment (see details in section *DRP installation*).

The next step is to download the data employed in this cookbook: [megara-cookbook-v2.tar.gz](https://gwaix.fis.ucm.es/data/megaradrp/megara-cookbook-v2.tar.gz)

If you find any trouble trying to download the previous file, try with the following command line:

```
(megara) $ curl -O https://gwaix.fis.ucm.es/data/megaradrp/megara-cookbook-v2.tar.gz
```

Warning: Please be aware that this file has been updated as of September 2024. This change has been motivated by the need to adapt the structure of the `control.yaml` file to facilitate the EMIR reduction pipeline in handling data obtained with a detector different from the one originally installed. This type of change requires the use of specific calibration files for the particular detector used at any given time. Once this file is modified for EMIR, MEGARA also inherits the same change (the different pipelines use the same Python package **numina** as the reduction launcher). The modification of the `control.yaml` file is not backward compatible, so it is necessary to have a recent version of `megaradrp` installed.

It is advisable to decompress the previous file in a pristine directory where you can comfortably start the reduction of the data:

```
(megara) $ tar zxvf megara-cookbook-v2.tar.gz
(megara) $ cd megara-cookbook-v2
(megara) $ source INSTALL.sh
```

The last command simply replaces the second line of the file `MEGARA/control.yaml` to set the proper directory where the cookbook data have been deployed.

5.2 Data organization

MEGARA DRP uses its own data organization to work.

```
(megara) $ tree -L 2
.
├── INSTALL.sh
├── MEGARA
│   └── M15_LCB_HR-R
```

(continues on next page)

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```

├── M71_MOS_LR-R
├── ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48
└── control.yaml

```

Note that the `tree` command shown above might not be available in certain unix distributions (you can use `ls` instead).

Under the `MEGARA/` directory we need to have the calibration tree with the specific name `ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/`, which is the string that uniquely identifies the instrument configuration (a different name was, for example, used during laboratory integration at LICA-UCM). Under the `MEGARA/` directory we can also have the requirements file named `control.yaml` needed to run the pipeline (see section *Running a recipe*).

The requirements file `control.yaml` contains the path for your `MEGARA/` directory (second line of this file; keyword `rootdir`), and useful information for performing the wavelength calibration of each VPH, including the number of arc lines and degree of polynomial fit to be used by the wavelength calibration recipe. In this file you can also specify the name for the extinction curve file used for the flux calibration recipe. This is simply an ASCII file with two space-separated columns, one with the wavelength in Angstroms and another with the magnitudes of extinction per unit airmass at the corresponding wavelength, i.e. the same format used for extinction curves within IRAF. We strongly recommend to use the standard extinction curve of the Roque de los Muchachos Observatory (file `extinction_LP.txt` under the `data` subdirectory; see below).

```

1 version: 1
2 rootdir: /Users/janedoe/megara-cookbook-v2
3 products:
4   MEGARA:
5     ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48:
6     - {id: 2, type: 'ReferenceExtinctionTable', tags: {}, content: 'extinction_LP.txt'}
7 requirements:
8   MEGARA:
9     ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48:
10    default:
11      MegaraArcCalibration:
12        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-U, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: LCB}, content: [25,
13        ↪25]}
14        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-U, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: MOS}, content: [25,
15        ↪25]}
16        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-B, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: LCB}, content: [10,
17        ↪10, 15, 5]}
18        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-B, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: MOS}, content: [10,
19        ↪10, 15, 5]}
20        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-V, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: LCB}, content: [15, 5,
21        ↪10, 7]}
22        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-V, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: MOS}, content: [15, 5,
23        ↪10, 7]}
24        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-R, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: LCB}, content: [14,
25        ↪7]}
26        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-R, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: MOS}, content: [14,
27        ↪7]}
28        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-I, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: LCB}, content: [14]}
29        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-I, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: MOS}, content: [14]}
30        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-Z, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: LCB}, content: [14,
31        ↪9]}
32        - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: LR-Z, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: MOS}, content: [14,

```

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```

24 ↪9]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-U, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: LCB}, content: [8,
25 ↪10]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-U, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: MOS}, content: [8,
26 ↪10]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-UB, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: LCB}, content: [20]]
27 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-UB, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: MOS}, content: [20]]
28 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-B, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: LCB}, content: [11]]
29 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-B, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: MOS}, content: [11]]
30 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-G, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: LCB}, content: [10,
31 ↪10,8]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-G, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: MOS}, content: [10,
32 ↪10,8]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-V, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: LCB}, content: [13,
33 ↪8]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-V, speclamp: ThAr, insmode: MOS}, content: [13,
34 ↪8]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-VR, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: LCB}, content: [14]]
35 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-VR, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: MOS}, content: [14]]
36 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-R, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: LCB}, content: [9]]
37 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-R, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: MOS}, content: [9]]
38 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-RI, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: LCB}, content: [7]]
39 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-RI, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: MOS}, content: [7]]
40 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-I, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: LCB}, content: [5,5,
41 ↪5]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-I, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: MOS}, content: [5,5,
42 ↪5]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-Z, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: LCB}, content: [4,5,
43 ↪3]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: MR-Z, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: MOS}, content: [4,5,
44 ↪3]]
    - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: HR-R, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: LCB}, content: [5]}
45 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: HR-R, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: MOS}, content: [5]}
46 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: HR-I, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: LCB}, content: [10]}
47 - {name: nlines, tags: {vph: HR-I, speclamp: ThNe, insmode: MOS}, content: [10]}
48 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: LR-U, speclamp: ThAr}, content: [3,5]}
49 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: LR-B, speclamp: ThAr}, content: [5,5]}
50 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: LR-V, speclamp: ThAr}, content: [5,5]}
51 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: LR-R, speclamp: ThAr}, content: [3,5]}
52 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: LR-I, speclamp: ThAr}, content: [3,5]}
53 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: LR-Z, speclamp: ThNe}, content: [3,5]}
54 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: MR-U, speclamp: ThAr}, content: [3,5]}
55 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: MR-UB, speclamp: ThAr}, content: [3,5]}
56 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: MR-B, speclamp: ThAr}, content: [3,5]}
57 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: MR-G, speclamp: ThAr}, content: [3,5]}
58 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: MR-V, speclamp: ThAr}, content: [3,5]}
59 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: MR-VR, speclamp: ThNe}, content: [3,5]}
60 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: MR-R, speclamp: ThNe}, content: [3,3]}
61 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: MR-RI, speclamp: ThNe}, content: [3,3]}
62 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: MR-I, speclamp: ThNe}, content: [3,5]}
63 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: MR-Z, speclamp: ThNe}, content: [3,3]}
64 - {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: HR-R, speclamp: ThNe}, content: [3,5]}

```

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```
- {name: polynomial_degree, tags: {vph: HR-I, specLamp: ThNe}, content: [3,5]}
```

Another fundamental function of the calibration tree (ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/) is to host the calibration products that will be used by the corresponding recipes, such as the **MasterBias**, **MasterFiberFlat**, **MasterSensitivity**, etc. Thus, once the files for these calibrations are generated, they should be copied under this calibration tree according structure below. Since the DRP would read the first file in alphabetical order inside the corresponding folder, we recommend to place only one file in each folder.

```
(megara) $ tree -L 2 ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48
ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48
├── LinesCatalog
│   ├── ThAr
│   └── ThNe
├── MasterBPM
│   └── master_bpm.fits
├── MasterBias
├── MasterFiberFlat
│   ├── LCB
│   └── MOS
├── MasterSensitivity
│   ├── LCB
│   └── MOS
├── MasterSlitFlat
├── MasterTwilightFlat
│   ├── LCB
│   └── MOS
├── ModelMap
│   ├── LCB
│   └── MOS
├── TraceMap
│   ├── LCB
│   └── MOS
└── WavelengthCalibration
    ├── LCB
    └── MOS
```

The content for the LinesCatalog/ is specific for each VPH (line lists for all VPHs can be found at <https://zenodo.org/record/2270518>). In the following example the calibration files for the HR-R (LCB observing mode) and LR-R (MOS observing mode) VPHs are shown. When other VPHs are used, the user just needs to create the corresponding folders. It is recommended to have only one file in each calibration directory. For example, for the same VPH you can have several `master_traces.json` files with the information to trace the fibers light through the detector at the same day but at different ambient temperatures.

Different files can be stored at the same directory, but the DRP is going to use the first file it encounters in alphabetical order. The user can name the desired file with prefix `00_` (e.g. `00_master_traces.json`) to be sure this is the file to be used by the DRP. Note that the sorting of files named `00_` and `000_` might be different for the operative system and for the MEGARA DRP, so avoid making abusive use of these prefixes.

An example of calibration tree with some additional calibration files is the following:

```
(megara) $ tree ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/ -L 4
ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/
├── LinesCatalog
```

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```

├── ThAr
│   ├── LR-R
│   │   └── LR-R_ThAr.lis
│   └── .
│       └── .
├── ThNe
│   ├── HR-R
│   │   └── HR-R_ThNe.lis
│   └── .
│       └── .
├── MasterBPM
│   └── master_bpm.fits
├── MasterBias
│   └── master_bias.fits
├── MasterFiberFlat
│   ├── LCB
│   │   ├── HR-R
│   │   └── master_fiberflat.fits
│   └── MOS
│       └── LR-R
│           └── master_fiberflat.fits
├── MasterSensitivity
│   ├── LCB
│   │   ├── HR-R
│   │   └── master_sensitivity.fits
│   └── MOS
│       └── LR-R
│           └── master_sensitivity.fits
├── MasterSlitFlat
├── MasterTwilightFlat
│   ├── LCB
│   │   ├── HR-R
│   │   └── master_twilightflat.fits
├── ModelMap
│   ├── LCB
│   │   ├── HR-R
│   │   └── master_model.json
│   └── MOS
│       └── LR-R
│           └── master_model.json
├── TraceMap
│   ├── LCB
│   │   ├── HR-R
│   │   └── master_traces.json
│   └── MOS
│       └── LR-R
│           └── master_traces.json
├── WavelengthCalibration
│   └── LCB

```

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```

├── HR-R
│   └── master_wlcalib.json
├── MOS
│   └── LR-R
│       └── master_wlcalib.json

```

Furthermore, the user's MEGARA/ directory can contain data for your targets under different directories (in this example our targets are the M15 and M71 globular clusters). **Your raw data should always be included in a subdirectory named data/** within each working target directory (M15, M71, etc.). Images could be stored gzipped but then the observation-result files should list the images with the .gz extension. The different observation-result files (*.yaml) used during the data reduction process should be also located within each target directory as they will be different for each target. In this example, the observation-result files in YAML format are named with a first number related in which order they are run.

```

(megara) $ tree M15_LCB_HR-R
M15_LCB_HR-R
├── 0_Bias.yaml
├── 1_TraceMap.yaml
├── 2_ModelMap.yaml
├── 3_WaveCalib.yaml
├── 3_WaveCalib_check.yaml
├── 4_FiberFlat.yaml
├── 5_TwilightFlat.yaml
├── 6_LcbAdquisition.yaml
├── 7_StandardStar.yaml
├── 8_LcbImage.yaml
├── data
│   ├── 0001251794-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits
│   ├── 0001251795-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits
│   ├── ...
│   ├── 0001312250-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
│   ├── 0001312251-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
│   ├── extinction_LP.txt
│   └── mbd284211_stis.dat

```

5.3 Running a recipe

The MEGARA DRP is run through a command line interface provided by **numina**.

Note: Remember that the numina script is the interface with GTC pipelines. In order to execute **megaradrp** recipes you should type something like:

```
(megara) $ numina run <observation_result_file.yaml> -r <requirements_file.yaml>
```

where **<observation_result_file.yaml>** is an observation result file in YAML format, and **<requirements_files.yaml>** is a requirements file, also in YAML format (this file is named **control.yaml**).

YAML is a human-readable data serialization language (for details see [YAML Syntax](#))

The run mode of numina requires:

- An observation-result file in YAML format.
- A requirements file in YAML format (`control.yaml`).
- The raw images obtained as part of the user's observing block.
- The calibrations required by the recipe.

The observation-result file and the requirements file are created by the user. This is an example of the observation result file to compute the fibers traces `1_TraceMap.yaml` under the subdirectory `M15_LCB-HR-R`:

```

1 id: 1_TraceMap_HR-R
2 mode: MegaraTraceMap
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5 - 0001312246-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
6 - 0001312247-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
7 - 0001312248-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits

```

The `id`: is an identifier of the observing block. The DRP will create two directories with the products of the recipe (`obsid<id>_work/` and `obsid<id>_results/`) using the `id` identifier as an arbitrary label to identify the corresponding processing block. The `mode`: is the name of the instrument observing mode as returned by `numina show-modes`. In `frames`: a list of the names of the images obtained as part of the observation should be included.

Using the same YAML file the user can process sequentially different sets of files with the same recipe. For that purpose, the `enabled`: parameter can be set to `True` (or `False`) to process (or not) a specific block of files. In this case, do not forget the separation line `---` between blocks (otherwise the pipeline will not recognize where one block ends and the next one begins). This separation line must not appear after the last block. Note that the user can add comments to these YAML files by adding lines preceded with a hash sign (`#`).

An example of an observation-result file with two blocks is the following:

```

(megara) $ more 1_TraceMap.yaml
id: 1_TraceMap_HR-R
mode: MegaraTraceMap
instrument: MEGARA
frames:
- 0001312246-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
- 0001312247-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
- 0001312248-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
enabled: True
---
id: 1_TraceMap_HR-R_d29jun
mode: MegaraTraceMap
instrument: MEGARA
frames:
- 0001252371-20170629-MEGARA-MegaraFiberFlatImage.fits
- 0001252372-20170629-MEGARA-MegaraFiberFlatImage.fits
- 0001252373-20170629-MEGARA-MegaraFiberFlatImage.fits
enabled: True

```

In the directory of our target M15 we have already defined several observation-result files (`*.yaml`):

```

(megara) $ pwd
/Users/janedoe/megara-cookbook-v2/MEGARA/M15_LCB_HR-R
(megara) $ ls
0_Bias.yaml          3_WaveCalib_check.yaml  7_StandardStar.yaml

```

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```
1_TraceMap.yaml      4_FiberFlat.yaml      8_LcbImage.yaml
2_ModelMap.yaml      5_TwilightFlat.yaml   data/
3_WaveCalib.yaml     6_LcbAdquisition.yaml
```

If we want to run the recipe **MegaraTraceMap** using the observing-result file `1_TraceMap.yaml`, with the requirements file `control.yaml` (the latter located in the directory above the current one), we should execute:

```
(megara) $ numina run 1_TraceMap.yaml -r ../control.yaml
```

When disk space is an issue, it is possible to execute `numina` indicating that links (instead of actual copies of the original raw files) must be placed in the `obsid<id>_work/` subdirectory. This behaviour is set using the parameter `--link-files`:

```
(megara) $ numina run 1_TraceMap.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

Other useful **numina** commands include:

```
(megara) $ numina show-modes
```

```
(megara) $ numina show-recipes
```

```
(megara) $ numina show-recipes -m <obs mode>
```

```
(megara) $ numina run -h
```

```
(megara) $ numina run 1_TraceMap.yaml -r ../control.yaml -enable <block_id>
```

5.4 Data reduction process

In the following sections the different steps to produce the target wavelength and flux calibrated row-stacked spectra (RSS) are detailed. The examples are illustrated making use of the cookbook data available for the target M15:

```
(megara) $ pwd
/Users/janedoe/megara-cookbook-v2/MEGARA/M15_LCB_HR-R
```

You can easily examine the header of the FITS images using the astropy utility `fitsheader`:

```
(megara) $ fitsheader -k VPH -k INSMODE -k OBJECT -k SPECLAMP -k EXPTIME -k DATE-OBS \
-f -e 0 data/*.fits
      filename                                VPH  INSMODE  OBJECT  SPECLAMP
--EXPTIME      DATE-OBS
-----
data/0001251794-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits  HR-R    LCB      NONE
60.0  2017-06-27T06:09:11.24
data/0001251795-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits  HR-R    LCB      NONE
60.0  2017-06-27T06:11:59.96
data/0001251796-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits  HR-R    LCB      NONE
60.0  2017-06-27T06:14:58.28
data/0001286973-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits  HR-R    LCB      BD28    NONE
200.0 2017-07-25T03:50:28.63
```

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data/0001286974-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits	HR-R	LCB	BD28	NONE
↳ 200.0 2017-07-25T03:55:02.94				
data/0001286975-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits	HR-R	LCB	BD28	NONE
↳ 200.0 2017-07-25T03:59:37.22				
data/0001309955-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits	HR-R	LCB	M15	NONE
↳ 60.0 2017-08-23T00:05:33.93				
data/0001309956-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits	HR-R	LCB	M15	NONE
↳ 60.0 2017-08-23T00:07:49.18				
data/0001309957-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits	HR-R	LCB	M15	NONE
↳ 60.0 2017-08-23T00:10:03.43				
data/0001310880-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits	MR-RI	LCB	Bias	NONE
↳ 0.0 2017-08-27T17:10:39.54				
data/0001310881-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits	MR-RI	LCB	Bias	NONE
↳ 0.0 2017-08-27T17:11:53.93				
data/0001310882-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits	MR-RI	LCB	Bias	NONE
↳ 0.0 2017-08-27T17:13:08.24				
data/0001310883-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits	MR-RI	LCB	Bias	NONE
↳ 0.0 2017-08-27T17:14:22.58				
data/0001310884-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits	MR-RI	LCB	Bias	NONE
↳ 0.0 2017-08-27T17:15:36.89				
data/0001310885-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits	MR-RI	LCB	Bias	NONE
↳ 0.0 2017-08-27T17:16:51.23				
data/0001310886-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits	MR-RI	LCB	Bias	NONE
↳ 0.0 2017-08-27T17:18:05.53				
data/0001310887-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits	MR-RI	LCB	Bias	NONE
↳ 0.0 2017-08-27T17:19:19.83				
data/0001310888-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits	MR-RI	LCB	Bias	NONE
↳ 0.0 2017-08-27T17:20:34.16				
data/0001312246-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits	HR-R	LCB	Halogen	NONE
↳ 5.0 2017-08-31T18:09:14.73				
data/0001312247-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits	HR-R	LCB	Halogen	NONE
↳ 5.0 2017-08-31T18:10:34.05				
data/0001312248-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits	HR-R	LCB	Halogen	NONE
↳ 5.0 2017-08-31T18:11:53.38				
data/0001312249-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits	HR-R	LCB	Halogen	ThNe
↳ 30.0 2017-08-31T18:13:38.10				
data/0001312250-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits	HR-R	LCB	Halogen	ThNe
↳ 30.0 2017-08-31T18:15:22.38				
data/0001312251-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits	HR-R	LCB	Halogen	ThNe
↳ 30.0 2017-08-31T18:17:06.67				
data/master_fiberflat_ones.fits	--	--	--	--
↳ --				

The data available include bias exposures (the VPH is not relevant here), halogen exposures (for tracing and flatfielding), ThNe arc exposures (for wavelength calibration), and target exposures.

5.4.1 Bias image

Before the Analog-to-Digital conversion is performed a pedestal (electronic) level is added to all images obtained with the MEGARA CCD. This is a standard procedure in CCD imaging and spectroscopy applications for Astronomy and is intended to minimize the ADC errors produced when very low analog values are converted to DUs. To calibrate this pedestal level of the detectors, bias images are taken with null integration time. We note the user that in the case of the MEGARA CCD (a 4k x 4k pixels CCD231-84 E2V chip), since the detector is always read using two diagonally-opposed amplifiers (to speed up the reading process while minimizing electronic cross-talk), the bias is slightly different in the upper and bottom halves of the image. Note that the Readout Noise (RoN) should be around $2 e^-$ in all cases.

This recipe processes a set of bias images obtained in Bias Image instrument mode. Images are corrected from overscan and trimmed to the physical size of the detector. Then, they are corrected from Bad-pixels Mask, if the BPM is available and finally, images are stacked using the median.

The content of the file `0_Bias.yaml` for the M15 data is the following:

```

1 id: 0_Bias
2 mode: MegaraBiasImage
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5 - 0001310880-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits
6 - 0001310881-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits
7 - 0001310882-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits
8 - 0001310883-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits
9 - 0001310884-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits
10 - 0001310885-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits
11 - 0001310886-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits
12 - 0001310887-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits
13 - 0001310888-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits

```

The recipe is run as follows,

```
(megara) $ numina run 0_Bias.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

and the products are stored in the directory `obsid0_Bias_results/`, including the `master_bias.fits` file (see [Figure 4](#)).

```

(megara) $ ls obsid0_Bias_work/
0001310880-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits@
0001310881-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits@
0001310882-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits@
0001310883-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits@
0001310884-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits@
0001310885-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits@
0001310886-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits@
0001310887-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits@
0001310888-20170827-MEGARA-MegaraBiasImage.fits@
index.pkl
master_bpm.fits@

(megara) $ ls obsid0_Bias_results/
master_bias.fits  processing.log  result.json  task.json

```

Note that the data files in the `obsid0_Bias_work` subdirectory are shown with a suffix `@`, indicating that these files are actually links to the original files (stored under the data subdirectory).

Figure 4: Example of a MEGARA master bias as created by the **MegaraBiasImage** recipe. Note that this image was obtained with the MEGARA DRP ver. 0.9. Later versions fit a spline to the overscan regions of both amplifiers (instead of adopting a constant value) so the resulting image is typically flatter than the example shown here.

The user needs to copy the file `master_bias.fits` to the calibration tree at `ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/MasterBias/`:

```
(megara) $ cp obsid0_Bias_results/master_bias.fits \
    ../ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/MasterBias
```

5.4.2 Dark image

The potential wells in CCD detectors spontaneously generate electron-ion pairs at a rate that is a function of temperature. For very long exposures this translates into a current that is associated with no light source and that is commonly referred to as dark current. Different tests during AIV activities have shown MEGARA detector's dark current has very low values $< 2 e^-/h/\text{pixel}$, therefore in our data reduction dark images are neither needed nor used.

5.4.3 Bad-pixels Mask

Although science-grade CCD detectors show very few bad pixels / bad columns there will be a number of pixels (among the ~17 Million pixels in the MEGARA CCD) whose response could not be corrected by means of using calibration images such as dark frames or flat-field images. These pixels, commonly called either dead or hot pixels, should be identified and masked so their expected signal could be derived using dithered images or, alternatively, locally interpolated. The user is provided with a Bad-Pixels Mask (BPM) named `master_bpm.fits` and located at `ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/MasterBPM/` that was generated as part of the AIV activities by processing a set of defocused continuum flat images. This image can be also found at <https://zenodo.org/record/2270518>. Currently, MEGARA presents only one (partial) bad column of 120 pixels in length.

5.4.4 Slit Flat correction

In the case of fiber-fed spectrographs the correction for the detector pixel-to-pixel variation of the sensibility is usually carried out using data from laboratory, where the change in efficiency of the detector at different wavelengths is computed and then used to correct for this effect for each specific instrument configuration (VPH setup in the case of MEGARA).

The quality of present-day CCDs leads to a rather small impact of these pixel-to-pixel variations in sensitivity on either the flux calibration and the cosmetics of the scientific images, especially considering that not one but a number of pixels along the spatial direction are extracted for each fiber and at each wavelength. In the case of MEGARA, the pseudo-slit has been offset from its optical focus position to ensure that the gaps between fibers are also illuminated when a continuum (halogen) lamp at the ICM is used. The results of the analysis of the pixel-to-pixel variations in sensitivity show that this correction is actually not needed although this recipe is implemented in the MEGARA DRP.

5.4.5 Tracing fibers

Trace map

The next processing step combine a series of fiber-flats to generate a master trace map. The fiber-flats are obtained by illuminating the instrument focal plane with a continuum (halogen) lamp that is part of the GTC Instrument Calibration Module (ICM).

This step produces the tracing information required to extract the flux of the fibers. The result is stored in a file named `master_traces.json`.

An example of the observation result file `1_TraceMap.yaml` to trace the fibers is the following:

```

1 id: 1_TraceMap_HR-R
2 mode: MegaraTraceMap
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5 - 0001312246-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
6 - 0001312247-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
7 - 0001312248-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits

```

Then the recipe is run by doing:

```
(megara) $ numina run 1_TraceMap.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

Images listed in the observation-result file are trimmed and corrected from overscan, bad-pixel mask (if `master_bpm.fits` is present in the calibration tree), bias and dark current (if `master_dark.fits` is present). Images thus corrected are then median stacked. The result of the combination is saved as an intermediate result that is named `reduced_image.fits`. This combined image is also returned in the field `reduced_image` of the recipe result and will be used for doing some quality control on the tracing of the fibers.

The fibers are then grouped in packs of different numbers of fibers. To match the traces in the image with the corresponding fibers, the DRP uses the information provided by the instrument configuration to know how fibers are packed and where the different groups of fibers appear in the detector. Using the column reference 2000, peaks are detected (using an average of 7 columns) and matched to the layout of fibers. Fibers without a matching peak are counted and their ids stored in the final `master_traces.json` file. Once the peaks in the reference column are found, each one is traced until the border of the image is reached. The trace may be lost before reaching the border. In all cases, the beginning and the end of the trace are stored.

The Y position of the trace is fitted to a polynomial of degree `polynomial_degree` set to 5 by default. The coefficients of the polynomial are stored in the final `master_traces.json` file.

```
(megara) $ ls obsid1_TraceMap_HR-R_work/
0001312246-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
0001312247-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
0001312248-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
cut_col2000_00_8b.png
cut_col2000_01_7b.png
cut_col2000_02_6b.png
cut_col2000_03_5b.png
cut_col2000_04_4b.png
cut_col2000_05_3b.png
cut_col2000_06_2b.png
cut_col2000_07_1b.png
cut_col2000_08_0.png
cut_col2000_09_1a.png
cut_col2000_10_2a.png
cut_col2000_11_3a.png
cut_col2000_12_4a.png
cut_col2000_13_5a.png
cut_col2000_14_6a.png
cut_col2000_15_7a.png
cut_col2000_16_8a.png
ds9.reg
ds9_raw.reg
frontiers_between_pseudoslits.png
index.pkl
master_bias.fits@
master_bpm.fits@
offset_borders_cross.png
reduced_image.fits
```

```
(megara) $ ls obsid1_TraceMap_HR-R_results
master_traces.json  reduced_image.fits  result.json
processing.log      reduced_rss.fits    task.json
```

The position of the fibers traces at the detector are shifted depending on the ambient temperature. It is recommended to have continuum halogen exposures near in time to the observation of the scientific target. If this is not the case, the traces can be shifted easily when processing the target (see below).

The traces generated by this task can be visualized both on the raw or the processed images and can be also shifted to consider possible offsets between these traces and the position in the fibers in other images (twilight flats, standard star or scientific target observations, etc.). The visualization of the traces and an underlying reduced image can be done by executing:

```
(megara) $ megaradrp-overplot_traces \
  obsid1_TraceMap_HR-R_results/reduced_image.fits \
  obsid1_TraceMap_HR-R_results/master_traces.json
```

It is also possible to overplot the traces in the original raw data, making use of the additional parameter `--rawimage`:

```
(megara) $ megaradrp-overplot_traces --rawimage \
  data/0001312246-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits \
  obsid1_TraceMap_HR-R_results/master_traces.json
```

respectively for the reduced and raw images. Another way to check the tracing is by overplotting the **ds9** region files

created by the DRP for the traces on top of this `reduced_image.fits` by doing (syntax might vary):

```
(megara) $ ds9 obsid1_TraceMap_HR-R_results/reduced_image.fits \
            -regions load obsid1_TraceMap_HR-R_work/ds9.reg
```

The same syntax can be used to check the offset between these traces and the position of the fibers in other images (arc-lamp, twilight, standard star and object images).

Finally, the user needs to copy this `master_traces.json` to the corresponding place at the calibration tree. In this case, this trace map corresponds to the VPH HR-R (LCB mode):

```
(megara) $ cp obsid1_TraceMap_HR-R_results/master_traces.json \
            ../ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/TraceMap/LCB/HR-R
```

Model map

This recipe processes a set of continuum flat images obtained in *Trace Map* or *Fiber Flat* modes and returns the fiber profile information required to perform **advanced** fiber extraction in other recipes.

The set of files listed in the observation-result file `2_ModelMap.yaml` is the same one used for the Trace Map.

```
1 id: 2_ModelMap_HR-R
2 mode: MegaraModelMap
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5 - 0001312246-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
6 - 0001312247-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
7 - 0001312248-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
```

Then the recipe is run by doing:

```
(megara) $ numina run 2_ModelMap.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

This processing step might take several minutes (from 10-40 min.) depending on the hardware used. When a model map is used the running times of the subsequent processing steps also increase by 2-5 minutes.

The images are processed as in the Trace Map recipe. In this case, the approximate central position of the fibers is obtained from the previously computed `master_traces.json`. Then, for every 100 columns of the reduced image, a vertical cut in the image is fitted to a sum of fiber profiles, being the profile a gaussian convolved with a square. After the columns are fitted, the profiles (central position and sigma) are interpolated to all columns using splines (see **Figure 5**). The coefficients of the resulting splines are stored in the final `master_model.json` file.

Figure 5: Mean position (left) and sigma (right) in pixels for fiber #310 along the spectral axis shown as blue points. The red line shows the spline fit. Plots for all the fibers are stored in the `obsid2_ModelMap_HR-R_work/` subdirectory.

The recipe also returns the RSS obtained by applying this advanced extraction to `reduced_image`. As an intermediate result, the recipe produces DS9 region files with the position of the center of the profiles, that can be used with raw and reduced images (see **Figure 6**).

Figure 6: MEGARA LCB HR-R continuum halogen exposure (left) and a region of the raw image (right) with the `ds9_raw.reg` tracing the fibers' path shown on top.

```
(megara) $ ls obsid2_ModelMap_HR-R_work/
0001312246-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
0001312247-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
0001312248-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
ds9.reg
ds9_raw.reg
fib_001_mean.png
fib_001_std.png
fib_002_mean.png
fib_002_std.png
...
...
fib_622_mean.png
fib_622_std.png
index.pkl
master_bias.fits@
master_bpm.fits@
reduced_image.fits
```

```
(megara) $ ls obsid2_ModelMap_HR-R_results/
master_model.json   reduced_image.fits  result.json
processing.log      reduced_rss.fits    task.json
```

The user needs to copy this `master_model.json` to the corresponding place at the calibration tree.

```
(megara) $ cp obsid2_ModelMap_HR-R_results/master_model.json \
  ../ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/ModelMap/LCB/HR-R
```

5.4.6 Wavelength Calibration

In this processing step the wavelength solution for each fiber is created using recipe **MegaraArcCalibration**. To create the dispersion solution the recipe needs raw arc-lamp frames as input (see **Figure 7**). Note that although the term used is “arc-lamps” these are ThAr and ThNe Hollow-Cathode Lamps (HCL).

Figure 7: MEGARA LCB ThNe arc-lamp exposure obtained with the HR-R VPH.

The user needs to check if the traces already computed in the previous step are appropriate to do the extraction in the arc-lamp exposures. If the continuum halogen used to generate the traces and the arc-lamp images were obtained near in time there no offset should be applied to the traces. By taking the images close in time user ensures that temperature remains constant so no offset is present. The offsets are estimated to be ~ 1 pixel per $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{K}$ of change in temperature. No offset in the spectral direction has been reported.

The user can check this and evaluate the actual offset by plotting the `ds9_raw.reg` regions file on top of the arc-lamp raw image using DS9. If the traces (regions in `ds9_raw.reg`) are above the fiber as seen in the raw image, then the offset is a negative number and it is measured in pixels, while if the traces are below then the offset is a positive number. This offset is given in the `requirements` section in the observation-result file using the `extraction_offset` parameter.

In this case, the observation-result file is called `3_WaveCalib.yaml`. In the example below, three frames for arc lamp exposures are included and the offset for the extraction is set to 0 pixels:

```
1 id: 3_WaveCalib_HR-R
2 mode: MegaraArcCalibration
```

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```

3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5 - 0001312249-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
6 - 0001312250-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
7 - 0001312251-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
8 requirements:
9 extraction_offset: [0.0]
10 store_pdf_with_refined_fits: 1

```

Then the recipe is run by doing:

```
(megara) $ numina run 3_WaveCalib.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

Images provided in `3_WaveCalib.yaml` are trimmed and corrected from overscan, bad-pixel mask (if `master_bpm.fits` is present in the calibration tree), bias and dark current (if `master_dark.fits` is present). The corrected images are then stacked using a median. The result of the combination of these images is saved as an intermediate result, named `reduced_image.fits`. The apertures in the 2D image are extracted, using the information in `master_traces.json` (or in the `model_map.json` if this file is present at the calibration tree) and the `extraction_offset` parameter set in the `3_WaveCalib.yaml`. The result of the extraction is saved as an intermediate result named `reduced_rss.fits`. The requirement file `control.yaml` has useful information for the wavelength calibration. For each fiber in the reduced RSS, the peaks are detected and sorted by peak intensity. Then, a total of `nlines` as listed in the `control.yaml` file are used to select the brightest peaks. If it is a list, then the peaks are divided, by their position, in as many groups as elements in the list, and `nlines[0]` peaks are selected in the first group, `nlines[1]` peaks in the second, etc. The selected peaks are then matched against the catalog of lines located in the calibration tree at `ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/LinesCatalog/`. The wavelengths of the matched features are fitted to a polynomial of degree equal to `polynomial_degree`. The matched lines, the quality of the match and other relevant information such as the coefficients of the polynomial are stored in the final `master_wlcalib.json` for each fiber.

Finally, the recipe returns different products. At the `obsid3_WaveCalib_HR-R_work/` directory the files `wavecal_iter1.pdf` (for the initial wavelength calibration) and `wavecal_iter2.pdf` (for the final iteration) contain a graphical representation for the wavelength calibration for each fiber. For example, in `wavecal_iter2.pdf` the total number of lines used for the refined wavelength calibration and the root mean square for each fit is plotted depending on the fiber number. In the same PDF file, the linear approximation for CRVAL1 and CDELTA1 is plotted and also a graph for each coefficient (typically of 5th degree) of the polynomial fit used for the refined wavelength calibration is shown (see **Figure 8**).

After the previous procedure, a refinement of the wavelength calibration is performed by fitting a polynomial to the variation of each coefficient of the wavelength calibration polynomial against the fiber number. Fibers whose wavelength calibration polynomial does not fit the expected smooth variation of the coefficients are automatically detected. In such cases, an interpolated polynomial is used, which provides very good results. The results of this refinement are graphically stored in the file `wavecal_refine_iter1.pdf`.

Figure 8: Some of the plots included in the `wavecalib_iter2.pdf` file generated with the **MegaraArcCalibration** recipe.

Should the user set the `store_pdf_with_refined_fits` parameter to `store_pdf_with_refined_fits: 1` at the `3_WaveCalib.yaml1`, the recipe will create the subdirectory `obsid3_WaveCalib_HR-R_work/refined_wavecal/` where a collection of PDF files (one for each fiber) is created with graphical information about the refined wavelength calibration (see **Figure 9**).

Figure 9: Example of the refined wavelength calibration result for fiber #310. This kind of file (310.pdf at refined_wavecalib/ in this case) is generated when the parameter store_pdf_with_refined_fits is set to 1. This requirement should be set to 0 for a faster execution of this recipe.

```
(megara) $ ls obsid3_WaveCalib_HR-R_work/
0001312249-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
0001312250-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
0001312251-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
index.pkl
initial_master_wlcalib.json
master_bias.fits@
master_bpm.fits@
reduced_image.fits
reduced_rss.fits
refined_wavecal/
wavecal_iter1.pdf
wavecal_iter2.pdf
wavecal_refine_iter1.pdf
```

```
(megara) $ ls obsid3_WaveCalib_HR-R_results/
fwhm_image.fits      reduced_image.fits  task.json
master_wlcalib.json  reduced_rss.fits
processing.log        result.json
```

The user needs to copy the master_wlcalib.json at the obsid_result/ directory to the corresponding place at the calibration tree:

```
(megara) $ cp obsid3_WaveCalib_HR-R_results/master_wlcalib.json \
  ../ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/WavelengthCalibration/LCB/HR-R
```

To quickly check the wavelength calibration, it is possible to apply the newly calculated calibration to the arc image itself. To do this, we can reduce the arc exposures as if they were scientific exposures. We carry out this task using the **MegaraLcbAcquisition** recipe. In this example, we execute this task using the file `3_WaveCalib_check.yaml`.

```
1 id: 3_WaveCalib_check_HR-R
2 mode: MegaraLcbAcquisition
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5 - 0001312249-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
6 - 0001312250-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
7 - 0001312251-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
8 requirements:
9 extraction_offset: [0.0]
10 master_fiberflat: master_fiberflat_ones.fits
```

Note that the images to be reduced correspond to the 3 individual arc exposures. Among the requirements, we are using `master_fiberflat: master_fiberflat_ones.fits`, a special FITS file located in the data subdirectory that contains a fictitious flatfield image where all values are set to 1.0. For the wavelength calibration check, we do not need to use a correct master fiberflat image.

Then the recipe is run by doing:

```
(megara) $ numina run 3_WaveCalib_check.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

The image to be examined is `obsid3_WaveCalib_check_HR-R_results/reduced_rss.fits`. In this image, all the arc line must appear as perfectly vertical lines.

```
(megara) $ numina-ximshow obsid3_WaveCalib_check_HR-R_results/reduced_rss.fits
```


5.4.7 Flat-field correction

Each optical fiber in MEGARA behaves like a different optical system, and therefore, its optical transmission is different and individual, with different wavelength dependence.

The recipe `MegaraFiberFlatImage` computes the `master_fiberflat.fits` to correct for the global variations in transmission in between fibers and as a function of wavelength in MEGARA. A fiber-flat image should be used to perform this correction. These images are obtained by means of illuminating the instrument focal plane with a flat spectral source (typically a halogen lamp) that is installed as part of the GTC Instrument Calibration Module (ICM).

In this case, we called the observation result file `4_FiberFlat.yaml`, where a total of three continuum halogen exposures are included:

```

1 id: 4_FiberFlat_HR-R
2 mode: MegaraFiberFlatImage
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5   - 0001312246-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
6   - 0001312247-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
7   - 0001312248-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits
8 requirements:
9 extraction_offset: [0.0]
```

If the inputs frames are the same used to trace the fiber spectra on the detector for the same specific spectral setup, the

extraction_offset parameter should be set to 0 pixels. If that is not the case the offset should be evaluated and computed as detailed in Section [Wavelength Calibration](#).

Then the recipe is run by doing:

```
(megara) $ numina run 4_FiberFlat.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

All images listed in the observation-result file are trimmed and corrected from overscan, bad pixel mask (if `master_bpm.fits` is present in the calibration tree), bias and dark current (if `master_dark.fits` is present) and corrected from pixel-to-pixel flat if `master_slitflat.fits` is provided. The corrected images are then stacked using a median. The result of the combination is saved as an intermediate result, named `reduced_image.fits`.

The apertures in the 2D image are extracted, using the information in `master_traces.json` (or in the `model_map.json` if this file is present at the calibration tree) and the `extraction_offset` parameter set in the `4_FiberFlat.yaml`, and then it is resampled according to the wavelength calibration in `master_wlcalib.json`. The resulting RSS is saved as an intermediate result named `reduced_rss.fits`. To normalize the master_fiberflat, each fiber is divided by the best-fitting spline to the average of all valid fibers (see [Figure 10](#)). The RSS image `master_fiberflat.fits` is returned as a recipe result (see [Figure 11](#)).

Figure 10: Example of the `collapsed_smooth.png` file generated as part of the `MegaraFiberFlatImage` recipe, which is located at the `obsid4_FiberFlat_HR-R_work/` directory. The green line is a spline fit to the average of all valid fibers, which is then used to normalize the extracted spectra in order to generate the normalized master_fiberflat image.

Figure 11: Example of the `master_fiberflat.fits` file generated for MEGARA LCB HR-R mode.

```
(megara) $ ls obsid4_FiberFlat_HR-R_work/
0001312246-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
0001312247-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
0001312248-20170831-MEGARA-MegaraSuccess.fits@
collapse.txt
```

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```

collapsed_smooth.png
index.pkl
mask_noinfo.txt
master_bias.fits@
master_bpm.fits@
reduced_image.fits
reduced_rss.fits

```

```

(megara) $ ls obsid4_FiberFlat_HR-R_results/
master_fiberflat.fits  reduced_image.fits  result.json
processing.log         reduced_rss.fits    task.json

```

The user needs to copy the `master_fiberflat.fits` to the corresponding place at the calibration tree:

```

(megara) $ cp obsid4_FiberFlat_HR-R_results/master_fiberflat.fits \
  ../ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/MasterFiberFlat/LCB/HR-R

```

5.4.8 Illumination correction

Blank twilight-sky exposures are to be used to calibrate the global change in response introduced by the fiber flat. This is called the illumination correction and it is due to the fact that the GTC ICM does not produce a perfectly uniform illumination of the field and that the fraction and shape of the pupil that is seen by the MEGARA fibers during the observation of a specific target does not coincide with that seen during the acquisition of the fiber-flat images with the ICM.

The twilight sky exposure can safely assume to homogeneously illuminate the entire MEGARA field of view (3.5 arcmin x 3.5 arcmin for MOS mode and 12.5 x 11.3 sq. arcsec for LCB mode). However, since the telescope pupil is not circular and the alignment of the image of the pupil on top fibers by the microlenses is not identical for all fibers, in order to do this correction properly, the Rotator Angle of the FC-F rotator (ROTANG keyword in the raw image) and the Elevation of the telescope (ELEVAT keyword), and ideally also the temperature, should have the same values as the ones for the scientific observation. Furthermore, in case of MOS observing mode, the twilight sky exposures should be done with the robotic positioners placed at the same positions as for the targets' configuration.

The recipe **MegaraTwilightFlatImage** process a set of continuum blank twilight sky images and returns the master twilight flat product. In this case, we named observation result file as `5_TwilightFlat.yaml`, where three frames for continuum blank twilight sky exposures being listed in the file:

```

1 id: 5_TwilightFlat_HR-R
2 mode: MegaraTwilightFlatImage
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5 - 0001251794-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits
6 - 0001251795-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits
7 - 0001251796-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits
8 requirements:
9   extraction_offset: [+2.5]
10  normalize_region: [1550, 1700]

```

The `extraction_offset` parameter can be computed as detailed in section [Wavelength Calibration](#) (see **Figure 12**).

Figure 12: Example of a region in the raw blank twilight sky image (LCB, HR-R) with the computed traces (ds9_raw.reg file) on top. In this case a `extraction_offset` of +2.5 pixels was needed.

Then the recipe is run by doing:

```
(megara) $ numina run 5_TwilightFlat.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

Images provided in the observation-result file are trimmed and corrected from overscan, bad pixel mask (if `master_bpm` is present), bias and dark current (if `master_dark` is present) and corrected from pixel-to-pixel flat if `master_slitflat` is provided. The corrected images are then stacked using a median. The result of the combination is saved as an intermediate result, named `reduced_image.fits`.

The apertures in the 2D image are extracted, using the information in `master_traces.json` (or in the `model_map.json` if this file is present at the calibration tree) and the `extraction_offset` parameter set in the `5_TwilightFlat.yaml`, and then it is resampled according to the wavelength calibration in `master_wlcalib.json`. Then, the result is divided by the `master_fiberflat`. The resulting RSS is saved as an intermediate result named `reduced_rss.fits`. To normalize the `master_twilightflat` (see **Figure 13**), each fiber is divided by the average of the column range given in `normalize_region` parameter in `5_TwilightFlat.yaml`. In those cases where the observation of an object includes a bright sky line, this `normalize_region` parameter can be used to obtain a twilight flat image from these science observations, especially if twilight frames of the same ROTANG, ELEVAT and temperature values are not available. In that case, the user can also make use of the parameter `continuum_region` to previously subtract the sky continuum under the bright sky line of interest. Note that the pixels used in the `normalize_region` and the `continuum_region` requirements correspond to those of the x-axis of the `reduced_rss.fits` image.

Figure 13: Example of the `master_twilightflat.fits` file generated for MEGARA LCB HR-R mode.

```
(megara) $ ls obsid5_TwilightFlat_HR-R_work/
0001251794-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits@
0001251795-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits@
0001251796-20170626-MEGARA-MegaraLCBImage.fits@
index.pkl
master_bias.fits@
```

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```

master_bpm.fits@
master_fiberflat.fits@
reduced_image.fits
reduced_rss.fits

```

```

(megara) $ ls obsid5_TwilightFlat_HR-R_results/
master_twilightflat.fits  reduced_rss.fits
processing.log            result.json
reduced_image.fits       task.json

```

The user needs to copy the `master_twilightflat.fits` at the `obsid5_TwilightFlat_HR-R_results/` directory to the corresponding place at the calibration tree:

```

(megara) $ cp obsid5_TwilightFlat_HR-R_results/master_twilightflat.fits \
  ../ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/MasterTwilightFlat/LCB/HR-R

```

5.4.9 Flux calibration

The flux calibration is performed by observing one or several spectrophotometric stars with the same instrument configuration that for the scientific observations. Depending on the number of standard stars observed and on the weather conditions (mainly transparency) two different types of calibration could be achieved:

- Absolute-flux calibration: The weather conditions during the night should be photometric and a number of spectrophotometric standard stars at different airmasses should be observed. This allows to fully correct from DUs per CCD pixel to energy surface density (typically in AB magnitudes, Jankys or $\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{\AA}^{-1}$) incident at the top of the atmosphere. If only one single standard star is observed (ideally at the airmass of the science object) this correction allows deriving the energy surface density hitting the telescope primary mirror exclusively, unless an atmospheric extinction curve for the observatory and that particular night is assumed (in which case the airmass could be different). In order to properly flux-calibrate scientific observations at all airmasses several stars should be observed during the night.
- Relative-flux calibration: If the weather conditions are not photometric this correction only allows normalizing the DUs per CCD pixel along the spectral direction so the conversion to incident energy at the top of the atmosphere is the same at all wavelengths. In order for this calibration to be valid one must assume that the effect of the atmosphere (including atmospheric cirrus and possibly thick clouds) on the wavelength dependence of this correction is that given by the adopted atmospheric extinction curve, even if the absolute flux level is not.

In the following, the different steps to do an absolute flux calibration are described. A photometric night and one spectrophotometric standard star observation with the same airmass as the scientific observation are assumed.

The entire flux of the spectrophotometric standard star needs to be recovered, so the LCB IFU bundle must be used. The recipe **MegaraLcbAcquisition** is used to process and extract the spectra in the standard star observation and determine the position of the centroid of the target in the LCB field of view, around which the total flux of the star will be later recovered.

In this case, the observation-result file for determining the star centroid is `6_LcbAdquisition.yaml`, where three frames for spectrophotometric standard star exposures are here listed:

```

1 id: 6_LcbImage_HR-R
2 mode: MegaraLcbAcquisition
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5 - 0001286973-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits

```

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```

6 - 0001286974-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits
7 - 0001286975-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits
8 requirements:
9 extraction_offset: [+4.5]

```

The `extraction_offset` parameter can be computed as detailed in section *Wavelength Calibration*.

Then the recipe is run by doing:

```
(megara) $ numina run 6_LcbAcquisition.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

Images provided in observation-result file are trimmed and corrected from overscan, bad pixel mask (if `master_bpm.fits` is present in the calibration tree), bias and dark current (if `master_dark.fits` is present) and corrected from pixel-to-pixel flat if `master_slitflat.fits` is provided. The corrected images are then stacked using a median. The result of the combination is saved as an intermediate result, named `reduced_image.fits`.

The apertures in the 2D image are extracted, using the information in `master_traces.json` (or in the `model_map.json` if this file is present at the calibration tree) and the `extraction_offset` parameter set in the `6_LcbAcquisition.yaml`, and then it is resampled according to the wavelength calibration in `master_wlcalib.json`. Then it is divided by the `master_fiberflat.fits`. The resulting RSS is saved as an intermediate result named `reduced_rss.fits`.

The sky is subtracted by combining the 56 fibers dedicated for this purpose in the LCB mode. The RSS with sky subtracted is saved in a file named `final_rss.fits` as a result of the recipe. Then, the centroids around both the center of the field and the brightest spaxel are computed using up the signal from the 3 rings of fibers (37 fibers in total) around these two spaxels. The offsets needed to center the object (considered to be either the centroid around the central spaxel or, more likely, around the brightest spaxel) in the center of the LCB field are then returned both in mm and arcsec. This information is saved in the `processing.log` file at the `obsid6_LcbImage_HR-R_result/` directory.

```
(megara) $ ls obsid6_LcbImage_HR-R_work/
0001286973-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits@
0001286974-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits@
0001286975-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits@
index.pkl
master_bias.fits@
master_bpm.fits@
master_fiberflat.fits@
master_twilightflat.fits@
reduced_image.fits
reduced_rss.fits

```

```
(megara) $ ls obsid6_LcbImage_HR-R_results/
final_rss.fits      reduced_image.fits  result.json
processing.log      reduced_rss.fits    task.json

```

```
(megara) $ more obsid6_LcbImage_HR-R_results/processing.log
2024-10-15 15:42:50,808 - numina.user.baserun - INFO - running recipe
2024-10-15 15:42:50,808 - numina.recipes.megara - INFO - starting AC LCB reduction
...
...
...
2024-10-15 15:45:56,053 - numina.recipes.megara - INFO - end sky subtraction

```

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```

2024-10-15 15:45:56,354 - numina.recipes.megara - DEBUG - LCB configuration is b7dcd9d1-
↳0b60-4b43-b26e-d2c9868d5e20
2024-10-15 15:45:56,567 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - DEBUG - LCB configuration is
↳b7dcd9d1-0b60-4b43-b26e-d2c9868d5e20
2024-10-15 15:45:56,568 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - INFO - maximum flux in spaxel
↳311 -- unknown
2024-10-15 15:45:56,851 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - DEBUG - LCB configuration is
↳b7dcd9d1-0b60-4b43-b26e-d2c9868d5e20
2024-10-15 15:45:56,852 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - DEBUG - adding 3 nrings
2024-10-15 15:45:56,852 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - DEBUG - adding 37 fibers
2024-10-15 15:45:56,852 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - INFO - Using 37 nearest fibers
2024-10-15 15:45:56,852 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - DEBUG - unit is arcsec
2024-10-15 15:45:56,852 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - INFO - For point [0.
↳465000003576279, 0.0] arcsec
2024-10-15 15:45:56,852 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - INFO - For point [0.
↳38366336928735895, 0.0] mm
2024-10-15 15:45:56,852 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - DEBUG - nearest fibers
2024-10-15 15:45:56,852 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - DEBUG - [311, 289, 333, 313,
↳310, 314, 308, 293, 329, 307, 316, 335, 312, 291, 331, 315, 309, 317, 305, 325, 297,
↳304, 319, 222, 400, 288, 334, 327, 295, 318, 306, 404, 218, 292, 330, 302, 320]
2024-10-15 15:45:56,853 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - INFO - centroid: [0.
↳36011112054854194, 0.052631794609784954] arcsec
2024-10-15 15:45:56,853 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - INFO - centroid: [0.
↳29712138659120624, 0.04342557311038363] mm
2024-10-15 15:45:56,853 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - INFO - 2nd order moments, x2=0.
↳354878, y2=0.353604, xy=-0.006228 arcsec^2
2024-10-15 15:45:56,853 - megaradrp.processing.centroid - INFO - FWHM , x=1.402805, y=1.
↳400284 arcsec

```

In this example, the brightest spaxel is located at $[0.38366336928735895, 0.0]$ mm relative to the center of the field, which is, by definition located at $[0.0, 0.0]$ mm. The position of the centroid obtained from the 37 fibers around this spaxels is $[0.29712138659120624, 0.04342557311038363]$ mm. **Note:** these numbers depend on whether you are using the trace map `master_traces.json` or the model map `master_model.json` (see section [Tracing fibers](#)).

This centroid offset (in mm) is needed to recover all the flux from the standard star and to derive the instrument sensitivity curve for a particular setup using the `MegaraLcbStdStar` recipe.

In this case, the observation-result file was named `7_StandardStar.yaml` and includes spectrophotometric standard star individual exposures:

```

1 id: 7_StandardStar_HR-R
2 mode: MegaraLcbStdStar
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5 - 0001286973-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits
6 - 0001286974-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits
7 - 0001286975-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits
8 requirements:
9 extraction_offset: [+4.5]
10 reference_spectrum: mbd284211_stis.dat
11 reference_extinction: extinction_LP.txt
12 position: [0.29712138659120624, 0.04342557311038363]
13 sigma_resolution: 100

```

The `extraction_offset` parameter can be computed as detailed in section *Wavelength Calibration* (this parameter is the same as in `6_LcbAcquisition.yaml` for the same spectrophotometric standard star). The parameter `reference_spectrum` includes a text file where the flux-calibrated spectrum in AB magnitudes is provided. (the format of these files is the same as for those found in the ESO spectrophotometric standard stars database located at this [ESO web page](#)). This parameter can be also specify in the `control.yaml`. The `reference_extinction` parameter points to the text file with the information to apply the atmospheric extinction correction. (for processing standard-star observations this parameter must be defined in either the `control.yaml` of `7_StandardStar.yaml` files or the recipe would fail; in the case of the **MegaraLcbImage** or **MegarMosImage** recipes this would only imply that the processed data would not be corrected for atmospheric extinction).

By default, the DRP searches for these data files in the `data/` directory. The `position` parameter is the position of the reference object, i.e. the offset in mm at the CCD detector computed with the recipe **MegaraLcbAcquisition**, written in the same format and units. Finally, the `sigma_resolution` parameter is the sigma of the Gaussian filter that would be used to degrade the resolution of the MEGARA input star spectrum. Given the high spectral resolution and low reciprocal dispersion of the MEGARA spectra this parameter is critical to remove artifacts associated to bright absorption lines present in the standard star spectrum, especially when the tabulated spectra have reciprocal dispersions that can be as high as 50 Å/pixel. The parameter `ignored_sky_bundles` contains the fiber bundle ids to be ignored when the sky spectrum is computed (see more details in section *LCB IFU/MOS scientific observation* below).

Then the recipe is run by doing:

```
(megara) $ numina run 7_StandardStar.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

Images provided in the observation-result file are trimmed and corrected from overscan, bad pixel mask (if `master_bpm.fits` is present in the calibration tree), bias and dark current (if `master_dark.fits` is present) and corrected from pixel-to-pixel flat if `master_slitflat.fits` is provided. The corrected images are then stacked using a median. The result of the combination is saved as an intermediate result, named `reduced_image.fits`.

The apertures in the 2D image are extracted, using the information in `master_traces.json` (or in the `model_map.json` if this file is present at the calibration tree) and the `extraction_offset` parameter set in the `7_StandardStar.yaml`, and then it is resampled according to the wavelength calibration in `master_wlcalib.json`. Then, the result is divided by the `master_fiberflat.fits`. The resulting RSS is saved as an intermediate result named `reduced_rss.fits`.

The sky is subtracted by combining the 56 fibers dedicated for this purpose in the LCB mode. The RSS with the sky already subtracted is saved in a file named `final_rss.fits` as a result of the recipe. The flux of the star is computed by summing the signal in 37 fibers around the spaxel closest to the offset given in the `position` parameter so, finally, the `star_spectrum.fits` is returned. This star spectrum is degraded with a Gaussian filter, corrected by atmospheric extinction and compared with the reference spectrum to return the `master_sensitivity.fits`, which is finally stored at the `obsid7_StandardStar_HR-R_result/` directory.

```
(megara) $ ls obsid7_StandardStar_HR-R_work/
0001286973-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits@
0001286974-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits@
0001286975-20170724-MEGARA-MegaraLcbImage.fits@
index.pkl
master_bias.fits@
master_bpm.fits@
master_fiberflat.fits@
master_twilightflat.fits@
reduced_image.fits
reduced_rss.fits
```

```
(megara) $ ls obsid7_StandardStar_HR-R_results/
fiber_ids.txt          reduced_image.fits    sky_rss.fits
```

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```

final_rss.fits          reduced_rss.fits      star_spectrum.fits
master_sensitivity.fits result.json           task.json
processing.log         sensitivity_raw.fits

```

The user can visualize the `master_sensitivity.fits` curve (see **Figure 14**) running the python script `megaratoools-plot_spectrum` that can be found in the DRP distribution located at <https://github.com/guaix-ucm/megara-tools> (see section *MEGARA Tools*).

```

(megara) $ megaratoools-plot_spectrum -s obsid7_StandardStar_HR-R_results/master_
↪sensitivity.fits

```


Figure 14: Example of sensitivity curve for MEGARA HR-R VPH. The spectral ranges defined by keywords `WAVLIMM1-2` and `WAVELIMF1-2` are shown as cyan and dashed brown lines, respectively (see text for details).

The user needs to copy the file `master_sensitivity.fits` to the calibration tree:

```

(megara) $ cp obsid7_StandardStar_HR-R_results/master_sensitivity.fits \
  ../ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/MasterSensitivity/LCB/HR-R/

```

It is worth noting that the `master_sensitivity.fits` file includes on its header the information on the spectral ranges that are valid in terms of spectral coverage both in pixels and wavelength for all, ranges covered in at least one fiber (`PIXLIMR1-2` and `WAVLIMR1-2`), all fibers (`PIXLIMM1-2` and `WAVLIMM1-2`) and with a proper flux calibration (`PIXLIMF1-2` and `WAVLIMF1-2`) (see **Table 2**). The latter range is limited by the degree of smoothing applied to the sensitivity curve. The `WAVLIMM1-2` and `WAVELIMF1-2` ranges are shown in **Figure 14** using cyan and dashed brown lines, respectively.

Keyword	Meaning	Keyword	Meaning
(keywords in pixels)		(keywords in Ångstroms)	
PIXLIMR1	Start of region with at least one fiber	WAVLIMR1	Start of region with at least one fiber
PIXLIMR2	End of region with at least one fiber	WAVLIMR2	End of region with at least one fiber
PIXLIMM1	Start of region with all fibers	WAVLIMM1	Start of region with all fibers
PIXLIMM2	End of region with all fibers	WAVLIMM2	End of region with all fibers
PIXLIMF1	Start of valid flux calibration	WAVLIMF1	Start of valid flux calibration
PIXLIMF2	End of valid flux calibration	WAVLIMF2	End of valid flux calibration

Table 2: Keywords included in the `master_sensitivity.fits` file regarding the wavelength coverage of at least one fiber (PIXLIMR1-2 and WAVLIMR1-2), all fibers (PIXLIMM1-2 and WAVLIMM1-2) and with proper flux calibration in all fibers (PIXLIMF1-2 and WAVLIMF1-2).

5.4.10 LCB IFU/MOS scientific observation

Once all the calibrations files are derived and copied at the corresponding calibration directories, the user can reduce the corresponding scientific observations with recipes **MegaraLcbImage** or **MegarMosImage** depending on the observing mode (the LCB IFU or the MOS).

In this case, the observation-result files are named `8_LcbImage.yaml` for the LCB and `8_MosImage.yaml` for the MOS mode, and include a list of all the frames obtained for the target. The `extraction_offset` parameter can be computed as detailed in section *Wavelength Calibration*. The `reference_extinction` parameter can be provided here if it is not at the `control.yaml` file. The parameter `ignored_sky_bundles` contains the sky bundle ids to be ignored when the sky spectrum is computed (see sample `.yaml` file below). In the case of LCB observing mode, the dedicated sky-bundles have, by default, all ids in the range 93-100. These bundles (sorted in blocks of seven consecutive fibers) correspond to the individual fiber ids and position on the sky (for instrument PA set to zero, i.e. NE) listed in Table below.

Sky-bundle id	Sky-fibers ids in each bundle	On-sky orientation for IPA=0°	Distance to the LCB center
93	22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28	NE	2.5 arcmin
94	57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63	E	1.75 arcmin
95	134, 135, 136, 137, 138, 139, 140	N	1.75 arcmin
96	267, 268, 269, 270, 271, 272, 273	SE	2.5 arcmin
97	351, 352, 353, 354, 355, 356, 357	NW	2.5 arcmin
98	484, 485, 486, 487, 488, 489, 490	S	1.75 arcmin
99	561, 562, 563, 564, 565, 566	W	1.75 arcmin
100	567, 596, 597, 598, 599, 600, 601, 602	SW	2.5 arcmin

Table 3: Sky bundles: The first column identifies the sky-bundle id, while the second column indicates which fibers (listed by fiber id) are included in each sky bundle. The orientation (for an instrument Position Angle of 0°, i.e. NE) and distance to the LCB center of each bundle is included in the third and fourth columns, respectively.

In case MOS observing mode, sky-bundles should have been previously selected by the user for that purpose when preparing the observation with FMAT tool. If no sky-bundles are identified the DRP will not perform any sky subtraction to the target data.

The content of the `8_LcbImage.yaml` file would be the following:

```

1 id: 8_LcbImage_HR-R_M15
2 mode: MegaraLcbImage
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5 - 0001309955-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits
6 - 0001309956-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits
7 - 0001309957-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits
8 requirements:
9 extraction_offset: [+6.5]
10 reference_extinction: extinction_LP.txt
11 ignored_sky_bundles: [93,95,98]
```

Then the recipe is run by doing:

```
(megara) $ numina run 8_LcbImage.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
```

Images provided in the observation-result file are trimmed and corrected from overscan, bad pixel mask (if `master_bpm.fits` is present in the calibration tree), bias and dark current (if `master_dark.fits` is present) and corrected from pixel-to-pixel flat if `master_slitflat.fits` is provided. The corrected images are then stacked using a median. The result of the combination is saved as an intermediate result, named `reduced_image.fits`.

The apertures in the 2D image are extracted, using the information in `master_traces.json` (or in the `model_map.json` if this file is present at the calibration tree) and the `extraction_offset` parameter set in the `8_LcbImage.yaml`. These are then resampled according to the wavelength calibration in `master_wlcalib.json`. Then, the result is divided by the `master_fiberflat.fits`. The resulting RSS is saved as an intermediate result named `reduced_rss.fits`.

The sky is subtracted by combining the 56 fibers (except the fibers listed in the `ignored_sky_bundles` parameter) dedicated for this purpose in the LCB mode. In case MOS observing mode, the sky is subtracted combining the signal of the fiber bundles (SKY bundles) selected by the user when preparing the MOS observation. The RSS with sky subtracted is saved in a file named `final_rss.fits` as a result of the recipe.

If a `master_sensitivity.fits` is provided (optional), RSS products will be flux calibrated. If `reference_extinction` is provided (optional), `final_rss.fits` and `reduced_rss.fits` will be extinction corrected. Notice that `sky_rss.fits` is not corrected for extinction.

```
(megara) $ ls obsid8_LcbImage_HR-R_M15_work/
0001309955-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits@
0001309956-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits@
0001309957-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits@
index.pkl
master_bias.fits@
master_bpm.fits@
master_fiberflat.fits@
master_sensitivity.fits@
master_twilightflat.fits@
reduced_image.fits
reduced_rss.fits
```

```
(megara) $ ls obsid8_LcbImage_HR-R_M15_results/
final_rss.fits      reduced_image.fits  result.json         task.json
processing.log      reduced_rss.fits    sky_rss.fits
```


Figure 15: Example of the `final_rss.fits` (sky subtracted, wavelength and flux calibrated) file for object M15 in the HR-R setup and the LCB observing mode.

The following is an example of the products for M71 MOS observing mode data reduction:

```
(megara) $ ls obsid8_MosImage_LR-R_M71_work/
0001288184-20170731-MEGARA-MegaraMosImage.fits@
0001288185-20170731-MEGARA-MegaraMosImage.fits@
0001288186-20170731-MEGARA-MegaraMosImage.fits@
index.pkl
master_bias.fits@
master_bpm.fits@
master_fiberflat.fits@
master_sensitivity.fits@
reduced_image.fits
reduced_rss.fits
```

```
(megara) $ ls obsid8_MosImage_LR-R_M71_results/
final_rss.fits      reduced_image.fits  result.json        task.json
processing.log     reduced_rss.fits   sky_rss.fits
```


Figure 16: Example of the `final_rss.fits` (sky subtracted, wavelength and flux calibrated) file for object M71 with the LR-R setup and the MOS observing mode.

The user has also the option of running these recipes without performing any flux calibration. In order to do that one can simply add the following lines (shown highlighted below) in the corresponding YAML file:

```
1 id: 8_LcbImage_HR-R_M15
2 mode: MegaraLcbImage
3 instrument: MEGARA
4 frames:
5   - 0001309955-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits
6   - 0001309956-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits
7   - 0001309957-20170822-MEGARA-MegaraLcbAcquisition.fits
8 requirements:
9   extraction_offset: [+6.5]
10  reference_extinction: null
```

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```
11 master_sensitivity: null
12 ignored_sky_bundles: [93,95,98]
```


HEALING DEFECTIVE TRACES

On some occasions, the reduction recipe responsible for determining the spectral traces does not work correctly. This may be due to slight detector defocus and/or low signal at one of the ends of the observed spectral range. If the problem does not occur in too many fibers, we describe here a manual procedure that allows obtaining corrected traces for the poorly adjusted fibers, using the information from well-adjusted neighboring traces.

Note: Sometimes the problem is that we do not have an adequate trace file. For example, when using the VPH LR-U valid traces are not obtained for most of the fibers. In such cases, it is an excessive effort to manually fix the adjustment for each fiber. The best alternative is to reuse an existing trace file and try to transform it for the exposures we need to calibrate. At the end of this page, in the *Obtaining traces for LR-U* section, we show an example of how to do this.

6.1 Identifying defective traces

Following the instructions in Section *Tracing fibers*, we look at the reduction step where the traces are determined, e.g.

```
(megara) $ numina run 1_tracemap.yaml --link-files -r ../control.yaml
...
...
INFO: start trace recipe QC
/Users/cardiel/s/megaradrp/src/megaradrp/recipes/calibration/trace.py:142: UserWarning:␣
↪In fiber 603, trace end < 4090
  warnings.warn(msg)
/Users/cardiel/s/megaradrp/src/megaradrp/recipes/calibration/trace.py:142: UserWarning:␣
↪In fiber 604, trace end < 4090
  warnings.warn(msg)
/Users/cardiel/s/megaradrp/src/megaradrp/recipes/calibration/trace.py:142: UserWarning:␣
↪In fiber 606, trace end < 4090
  warnings.warn(msg)
/Users/cardiel/s/megaradrp/src/megaradrp/recipes/calibration/trace.py:142: UserWarning:␣
↪In fiber 607, trace end < 4090
  warnings.warn(msg)
/Users/cardiel/s/megaradrp/src/megaradrp/recipes/calibration/trace.py:142: UserWarning:␣
↪In fiber 610, trace end < 4090
  warnings.warn(msg)
/Users/cardiel/s/megaradrp/src/megaradrp/recipes/calibration/trace.py:138: UserWarning:␣
↪In fiber 614, trace start > 6
  warnings.warn(msg)
/Users/cardiel/s/megaradrp/src/megaradrp/recipes/calibration/trace.py:142: UserWarning:␣
```

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```

↪In fiber 614, trace end < 4090
  warnings.warn(msg)
INFO: Result QC is QC.PARTIAL
INFO: end trace recipe QC
INFO: storing result uuid=447a0a48-025b-11ef-9801-a860b6166057, quality=QC.PARTIAL
INFO: with field master_traces=TraceMap(instrument=MEGARA, uuid=40959c26-025b-11ef-9801-
↪a860b6166057), quality=QC.PARTIAL
INFO: storing task id=02_tracemap

```

Please note that the execution of the last command has generated an on-screen output indicating that the traces of some fibers have encountered issues. Specifically, the affected fibers are: 603, 604, 606, 607, 610, and 614.

Move to the subdirectory with the results from the previous step.

```
(megara) $ cd obsidl_LR-R_tracemap_results/
```

Identifying faulty traces is straightforward using the `megaradrp-overplot_traces` script.

```

(megara) $ megaradrp-overplot_traces reduced_image.fits master_traces.json
>>> File..: reduced_image.fits
>>> MAXIS1: 4096
>>> MAXIS2: 4112

* Fiber description for INSMODE=LCB
Box 8a,  fibers 603 - 623
Box 7a,  fibers 582 - 602
Box 6a,  fibers 561 - 581
Box 5a,  fibers 533 - 560
Box 4a,  fibers 505 - 532
Box 3a,  fibers 470 - 504
Box 2a,  fibers 428 - 469
Box 1a,  fibers 351 - 427
Box  0,  fibers 274 - 350
Box 1b,  fibers 197 - 273
Box 2b,  fibers 155 - 196
Box 3b,  fibers 120 - 154
Box 4b,  fibers  92 - 119
Box 5b,  fibers  64 -  91
Box 6b,  fibers  43 -  63
Box 7b,  fibers  22 -  42
Box 8b,  fibers   1 -  21

-----
>>> Using global_offset: 0.0
Warning ---> Missing fiber: 614  [8a]
Warning ---> Missing fiber: 623  [8a]
Press "q" to continue...

```


Although the traces appear to be correctly calculated, when zooming in on the fibers corresponding to Box 8a, we can see that there are several fibers whose traces have not been calculated correctly. We can zoom in on the matplotlib image using the magnifying glass tool, or we can run the previous script using the `--bbox` parameter, which takes a list with 4 numbers (`xmin`, `xmax`, `ymin`, `ymax`). We also add the `--fibids` parameter, which enables displaying the fiber number in the same figure.

```
(megara) $ megaradrp-overplot_traces reduced_image.fits master_traces.json \
--fibids \
--bbox 1,4096,3775,3950
...
```


The trace signal fades for X values around the range [2500, 3500], causing some traces to end prematurely (fibers 603, 604, 606, 607, 610), to switch fibers (e.g., the trace for fiber 613 jumps to the position of fiber 614), or even for the trace to fail to be calculated (fiber 614). Not surprisingly, these are the same fibers with issues in the execution of the **MegaraTraceMap** recipe.

The next section describes the different strategies that can be employed to fix wrong (or even missing) traces.

6.2 Strategies to fix defective traces

The `megaradrp-heal_traces` script helps recover miscalculated traces using different options. An example of execution is as follows:

```
(megara) $ megaradrp-heal_traces reduced_image.fits master_traces.json \
--fibids --healing healing.yaml \
--updated_traces master_traces_healed.json
```

The first two parameters are the same as those used with the `megaradrp-overplot_traces` script (the FITS image and the JSON file with information about the calculated traces). The new relevant parameters are:

- `--healing <healing.yaml>`: specifies the name of a YAML file that defines the strategy for correcting erroneous traces. The format of this file is explained in more detail below.
- `--updated_traces <master_traces_healed.json>`: specifies the name of the JSON file that will store the corrected version of all traces.

With the help of the <healing.yaml> file, we can make use of different strategies to correct faulty traces. These strategies are indicated in the YAML file using the tag `description`. The corrections to be applied to calculate the new trace for each fiber are included in the YAML file in independent blocks separated by the usual YAML separator `---` (see a more detailed example in the next section).

Next we show the different possibilities with some example numbers.

6.2.1 sandwich

Useful for defining a trace using information from two neighboring traces.

```
description: sandwich
fibid: 610
fraction: 0.5
neighbours: [609, 611]
xstart: 6
xstop: 4090
```


In the example, the corrected trace for `fibid: 610` (green dotted line) is calculated halfway between the position of the trace for fiber 609 and fiber 611. The `fraction` tag equal to 0.5 indicates that the new trace is equidistant from the other two. This fraction number can be varied to obtain traces that are not equidistant from the two reference traces. For example, `fraction=0.33333` would make the new trace one-third of the distance from the first fiber indicated in the tag `neighbours`. The `xstart` and `xstop` tags indicate the X coordinate where the new trace will be valid.

6.2.2 extrapolation

This method enables the extrapolation of traces whose fitting is truncated on the X-axis.

```
description: extrapolation
fibid_ini: 610
fibid_end: 610
xstart: 6
xstop: 4090
```


In this approach, the fibers whose numbers are between `fibid_ini` and `fibid_end` are recomputed for X-axis values in the interval `[xstart, xstop]`. It is also possible to indicate a list of fibers using the tag `fibid_list` instead of the pair of tags `fibid_ini` and `fibid_end`.

In the example shown, only the initial fitting performed for fiber 610 (blue dotted line) has been extrapolated. It can be observed that the result (green dotted curve) is not optimal. It is likely that a simple extrapolation of the initially performed fitting will not be a good estimation of the trace in the regions where it has not been possible to determine the trace position. In general, it will be more useful to use the method described below.

6.2.3 extrapolation_through_user_points

This method offers a much more reliable extrapolation strategy because the user can define a set of additional points that are also used to fit the trace.

```
description: extrapolation_through_user_points
fibid: 603
xstart_reuse: 4
xstop_reuse: 2000
resampling: 20
poldeg: 5
xstart: 6
xstop: 4090
user_points:
  - [3500, 3817.0]
  - [4000, 3818.0]
refit: False
```


In the example shown, the extrapolation of the initial fitting for fiber 603 (blue dotted line) has been performed reusing the prediction of this initial fitting in the interval $[xstart_reuse, xstop_reuse]$. The resampling parameter indicates that 20 intermediate points (magenta filled circles) are calculated within this interval, which constitute the data that are actually used in the new fitting. In addition to these 20 points, the additional points (cyan filled circles) specified under the `user_points` tag are also added. The final result is evaluated for X-axis values between `xstart` and `xstop`.

The additional tag `refit` indicates whether after performing the requested fitting, the script recalculates the entire fitting

again, determining the maximum signal of each fiber, column by column in the image, and applying a polynomial fit by iteratively removing points that deviate more than 3 times the residual standard deviation. This method is slower but allows the final fit to be less sensitive to the user-entered values. In any case, it may be useful to compare the results obtained by setting `refit` to `True` or `False`.

6.2.4 `fit_through_user_points`

This option allows for the manual entry of all points to be used for fitting the trace.

```
description: fit_through_user_points
fibid: 603
poldeg: 5
xstart: 6
xstop: 4090
user_points:
- [100.0, 3796.8]
- [500.0, 3801.1]
- [1000.0, 3806.0]
- [1500.0, 3810.2]
- [2000.0, 3813.8]
- [3000.0, 3816.6]
- [3500.0, 3817.7]
- [4000.0, 3817.9]
refit: False
```


In the provided example, the coordinates of all the points to be fitted (cyan filled circles) for recalculating the trace of fiber 603 are entered under the `user_points` tag. The trace is determined as the polynomial of degree `poldeg`, evaluated in the interval `[xstart, xstop]`.

The additional tag `refit` indicates whether after performing the requested fitting, the script recalculates the entire fitting again, determining the maximum signal of each fiber, column by column in the image, and applying a polynomial fit by iteratively removing points that deviate more than 3 times the residual standard deviation. This method is slower but allows the final fit to be less sensitive to the user-entered values. In any case, it may be useful to compare the results obtained by setting `refit` to `True` or `False`.

6.2.5 vertical_shift_in_pixels

This method enables the vertical displacement of already fitted fiber traces.

```
description: vertical_shift_in_pixels
fibid_ini: 601
fibid_end: 602
vshift: 6
```


In this approach, the fibers whose numbers are between `fibid_ini` and `fibid_end` are vertically shifted by `vshift` pixels. It is also possible to indicate a list of fibers using the tag `fibid_list` instead of the pair of tags `fibid_ini` and `fibid_end`.

The provided example is merely an illustrative demonstration of what would happen if we vertically shifted the traces of fibers 601 and 602 by 6 pixels (in this case, the outcome would be non-beneficial as the displaced traces do not yield a useful result; it is only shown to verify that the procedure functions correctly).

6.2.6 duplicate_trace

This method duplicates the trace of a fiber and vertically displaces it.

```
description: duplicate_trace
fibid_original: 602
fibid_duplicated: 603
vshift: 13
```


In the provided example, the initial trace of fiber 602 duplicated and vertically shifted upwards by 13 pixels to replicate the trace of fiber 603.

6.2.7 renumber_fibids_within_box

This method enables the renumbering of fiber traces within the same box.

```
description: renumber_fibids_within_box
fibid_ini: 620
fibid_end: 622
fibid_shift: -1
```


In the provided example, the traces of 3 fibers (numbers 620, 621, and 622) are renumbered by subtracting 1 from the fiber number. The `fibid_shift` tag can only be set to -1 or +1. It is important to note that the renumbered traces all belong to fibers within the same box (8a in this particular case).

6.3 Fixing multiple traces at once

6.3.1 Bringing together all the corrections

In practical scenarios, it is common to need to fix multiple traces within a single image. As an example, let's revisit the case of the image shown below.

In such cases, it is convenient to gather the reconstruction of the traces that require recalculation into a single YAML file. We can combine the different strategies described in the previous section. In each case, it will be necessary to include the typical YAML separator `---` to indicate the different sections of the file.

```

1 description: extrapolation_through_user_points
2 fibid: 603
3 xstart_reuse: 4
4 xstop_reuse: 2000
5 resampling: 20
6 poldeg: 5
7 xstart: 6
8 xstop: 4090
9 user_points:
10   - [3500, 3817.0]
11   - [4000, 3818.0]
12 refit: False
13 ---
14 description: extrapolation_through_user_points
15 fibid: 604
16 xstart_reuse: 4
17 xstop_reuse: 2000
18 resampling: 20
19 poldeg: 5

```

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```
20 xstart: 6
21 xstop: 4090
22 user_points:
23   - [3500, 3823.2]
24   - [4000, 3824.2]
25 refit: False
26 ---
27 description: extrapolation_through_user_points
28 fibid: 606
29 xstart_reuse: 4
30 xstop_reuse: 2000
31 resampling: 20
32 poldeg: 5
33 xstart: 6
34 xstop: 4090
35 user_points:
36   - [3500, 3835.0]
37   - [4000, 3836.2]
38 refit: False
39 ---
40 description: sandwich
41 fibid: 607
42 fraction: 0.5
43 neighbours: [606, 608]
44 xstart: 6
45 xstop: 4090
46 ---
47 description: sandwich
48 fibid: 610
49 fraction: 0.5
50 neighbours: [609, 611]
51 xstart: 6
52 xstop: 4090
53 ---
54 description: extrapolation_through_user_points
55 fibid: 613
56 xstart_reuse: 4
57 xstop_reuse: 2000
58 resampling: 20
59 poldeg: 5
60 xstart: 6
61 xstop: 4090
62 user_points:
63   - [3500, 3878.1]
64   - [4000, 3878.6]
65 refit: False
66 ---
67 description: sandwich
68 fibid: 614
69 fraction: 0.5
70 neighbours: [613, 615]
71 xstart: 6
```

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72 **xstop: 4090**

If the previous transformations are saved into a file named `healing.yaml`, we can apply all the transformations with a simple execution of the script `megaradrp-heal_traces`:

```
(megara) $ megaradrp-heal_traces reduced_image.fits master_traces.json \
--fibids \
--healing healing.yaml \
--updated_traces master_traces_healed.json \
--bbox 1,4096,3775,3950 \
--verbose

>>> File..: reduced_image.fits
>>> NAXIS1: 4096
>>> NAXIS2: 4112

* Fiber description for INSMODE=LCB
Box 8a,  fibers 603 - 623
Box 7a,  fibers 582 - 602
Box 6a,  fibers 561 - 581
Box 5a,  fibers 533 - 560
Box 4a,  fibers 505 - 532
Box 3a,  fibers 470 - 504
Box 2a,  fibers 428 - 469
Box 1a,  fibers 351 - 427
Box 0,   fibers 274 - 350
Box 1b,  fibers 197 - 273
Box 2b,  fibers 155 - 196
Box 3b,  fibers 120 - 154
Box 4b,  fibers 92  - 119
Box 5b,  fibers 64  - 91
Box 6b,  fibers 43  - 63
Box 7b,  fibers 22  - 42
Box 8b,  fibers 1   - 21
-----
>>> Using global_offset: [0.0]
Warning ---> Missing fiber: 614 [8a]
Warning ---> Missing fiber: 623 [8a]
(extrapolation_through_user_points): 603 [8a]
(extrapolation_through_user_points): 604 [8a]
(extrapolation_through_user_points): 606 [8a]
(sandwich) fibid: 607 [8a]
(sandwich) fibid: 610 [8a]
(extrapolation_through_user_points): 613 [8a]
(sandwich) fibid: 614 [8a]
Press "q" to continue...
```


It is important to note that the script performs the calculation of the new traces sequentially, allowing a previously repaired trace to be used in a subsequent step. This behavior is exemplified by the fiber 606 in the provided example. The trace of this fiber 606 is first reconstructed using the `extrapolation_through_user_points` method. Subsequently, the obtained result is reused to recalculate the trace of fiber 607 using the `sandwich` method, which utilizes the new values of the trace of fiber 606 and the original trace of fiber 608.

6.3.2 Important: final check

During the execution of `megaradrp-heal_traces`, we utilized the parameter `--updated_traces master_traces_healed.json`, which specifies the name of the JSON file containing all the corrected traces. It is advisable to now employ this file in conjunction with the `megaradrp-overplot_traces` script to perform a final verification and ensure that all traces have been correctly corrected. This step is crucial since improper configuration of the `healing.yaml` file could lead to undesired outcomes.

```
(megara) $ megaradrp-overplot_traces reduced_image.fits master_traces_healed.json \
--fibids \
--bbox 1,4096,3775,3950
```

Please note that the second parameter is now `master_traces_healed.json` instead of `master_traces.json`. We have successfully corrected all the faulty traces, and the obtained result is satisfactory.

Warning: The newly created `master_traces_healed.json` file should now be copied to its intended location within the calibration tree. **When performing this operation, it is advisable to rename the destination file to ensure that the pipeline utilizes the corrected file (thereby overwriting the existing `master_traces.json` file in the destination location, if applicable).** For example (assuming we are calibrating traces corresponding to the LR-R VPH):

```
(megara) $ cp master_traces_healed.json \
  ../../MEGARA/ca3558e3-e50d-4bbc-86bd-da50a0998a48/TraceMap/LCB/LR-R/master_traces.
  ↪ json
```

The file `master_traces_healed.json` has a different uuid than the one assigned to the file `master_traces.json`.

6.4 Obtaining traces for LR-U

It is challenging to obtain good traces for the VPH LR-U because the continuous lamp usually employed to obtain fiber-flat exposures does not provide enough signal in the bluest region of the spectrum. For this reason, the **Megara-TraceMap** recipe does not provide acceptable traces for this VPH.

In such cases, we can use a historical trace file for this VPH (for example the file `master_traces_LRU_20220325.json` that can be downloaded [from this link](#)), obtained from twilight exposures with sufficient signal, and transform the location of these traces to match the fiber positions in fiber-flat (or science) images corresponding to our observation campaign.

In general, simply applying a vertical offset to the initial traces in `master_traces_LRU_20220325.json` will not be sufficient because we might achieve a good fit for the first fibers (those appearing at the bottom of the detector) but not for the last fibers (those appearing at the top). In this case, we can use the fact that the `global_offset` parameter of the `megaradrp-heal_traces` script accepts not only a real number but also several numbers, which represent the coefficients of a polynomial transformation that applies a slightly different vertical offset to each fiber. For example, the following code applies a vertical offset following a polynomial of the form $\text{vertical_offset} = 8.9 + 0.00060 \times y$, where y is the vertical coordinate (along NAXIS2) of the considered fiber, evaluated at the reference column (key `ref_column` in the JSON master traces files, which is typically set to 2000, the middle location along the wavelength axis, NAXIS1). The offset is calculated in pixel units.

```
(megara) $ megaradrp-heal_traces \
reduced_image.fits \
master_traces_LRU_20220325.json \
--global_offset 8.9 0.00060 \
--updated_traces master_traces_LRU_20220325_healed.json
```

The execution of this command opens a graphical window that, with the help of the zoom button, allows us to easily verify how well the numerical coefficients used for the `--global_offset` parameter work. Through trial and error, it is possible to refine these numbers until the desired result is achieved.

Note that the above command does not apply any of the strategies described in the previous subsection to try to correct individual fibers. That is, we are not using any file of the type `healing.yaml`. We are simply applying a different vertical offset to each fiber.

The file `master_traces_LRU_20220325_healed.json` will contain the resulting master traces after applying the mentioned mathematical transformation.

The newly created JSON file should now be copied to its intended location within the calibration tree (remember to rename the destination file as `master_traces.json` to avoid having several files in the same calibration subdirectory; see warning note in the previous subsection).

MEGARA TOOLS

In this section we describe a series of software tools that have been developed by the MEGARA team and that can be used to visualize and analyze the products of the MEGARA DRP. The first two tools (visualization and cube) are already included as part of the MEGARA DRP distribution. The rest conform their own software package **megara-tools**, which is also available through GitHub at <https://github.com/guaix-ucm/megara-tools>. The installation requires to follow one of these three strategies:

To install the latest stable version:

```
(megara) $ pip install megara-tools[hypercube]

# Note: mac OS under zsh should use:
# $ pip install "megara-tools[hypercube]"
```

or, if you do not want **hypercube** to be installed (as it includes **pysynphot** as a dependency, which is no longer actively developed), simply do:

```
(megara) $ pip install megara-tools
```

To install the development version:

```
(megara) $ pip install git+https://github.com/guaix-ucm/megara-tools.git
```

To develop your own tools based on **megara-tools**:

```
(megara) $ git clone https://github.com/guaix-ucm/megara-tools.git
(megara) $ cd megara-tools
(megara) $ pip install -e .
```

All tools described in this section should be under Python ≥ 3.5 and should be run within the MEGARA DRP environment. For all tools besides **megarertools-cube** and **megarertools-hypercube**, these can be run under the **megaradrp** Python package (**numina** and **megaradrp** versions 0.21+ and 0.9+, respectively) or under the development version. For **megarertools-cube** and **megarertools-hypercube**, the development version or Python packages with release date after July 1st 2020 (**numina** and **megaradrp** versions 0.22+ and 0.10+, respectively) should be used. All these tools have been extensively tested in Mac OS X (10.10 to 10.15) and linux machines. Some of the examples below make use of `test/*` folder data that are downloaded when executing the code tests.

7.1 Downloading sample data

The sample data employed in this section is available at this link: [test-megaratoools_v1.tar.gz](https://guaix.fis.ucm.es/data/megaradrp/test-megaratoools_v1.tar.gz)

If you find any trouble trying to download the previous file, try with the following command line:

```
(megara) $ curl -O https://guaix.fis.ucm.es/data/megaradrp/test-megaratoools_v1.tar.gz
```

After decompressing and extracting the contents of this file, you should generate a subdirectory `test/` with all the sample files required in the following examples.

7.2 Megaradrp.Visualization

As part of the MEGARA DRP we also provide a tool to visualize the RSS frames generated when processing LCB IFU data. This tool is best suited for visualizing `final_rss.fits` RSS images (or, equivalently, `reduced_rss.fits` images) obtained after running the **MegaraLcbImage** processing recipe. The way to execute this code is to use the following command under the corresponding MEGARA environment:

```
(megara) $ python -m megaradrp.visualization \
test/final_rss_M32_MR-G.fits --label "flux (Jy)" --wcs-grid
```


Figure 17: Example of reconstructed `final_rss.fits` (sky subtracted, wavelength and flux calibrated) image of the center of Local Group galaxy M32 in the MR-G setup. This image is generated using the `megaradrp.visualization` code included in the MEGARA DRP distribution.

```
(megara) $ python -m megaradrp.visualization \
test/final_rss_M15_HR-R.fits --label "flux (Jy)" --wcs-grid
```


Figure 18: Example of reconstructed `final_rss.fits` (sky subtracted, wavelength and flux calibrated) image of the center of globular cluster M15 in the HR-R setup. This image is generated using the `megaradrp-visualization` code included in the MEGARA DRP distribution.

Figures 17 and 18 show two examples of the output generated by this code for commissioning observations of Local Group galaxy M32 and Galactic Globular Cluster M15, respectively.

As for the other commands, adding the `-h` flag would provide the help and syntax for using this command. The result is the following:

```
(megara) $ python -m megaradrp.visualization --help
usage: visualization.py [-h] [--wcs-grid] [--wcs-pa-from-header]
                        [--fix-missing]
                        [--average-region AVERAGE_REGION AVERAGE_REGION]
                        [--extname EXTNAME] [--column COLUMN]
                        [--continuum-region CONTINUUM_REGION CONTINUUM_REGION]
                        [--coordinate-type {pixel,wcs}] [--colormap COLORMAP]
                        [--plot-sky] [--display-fibid] [--plot-nominal-config]
                        [--hide-values] [--title TITLE] [--label LABEL]
                        [--hex-size HEX_SIZE] [--hex-rel-size HEX_REL_SIZE]
                        [--min-cut MIN_CUT] [--max-cut MAX_CUT]
                        [--percent PERCENT]
                        [--stretch {linear,sqrt,power,log,asinh}]
                        [--contour-pixel-size CONTOUR_PIXEL_SIZE]
                        [--contour-levels CONTOUR_LEVELS] [--contour]
                        [--contour-image CONTOUR_IMAGE]
                        [--contour-image-column CONTOUR_IMAGE_COLUMN]
                        [--contour-image-save CONTOUR_IMAGE_SAVE]
                        [--contour-image-region CONTOUR_IMAGE_REGION CONTOUR_IMAGE_
↪ REGION]
                        [--contour-is-density]
                        RSS [RSS ...]

Display MEGARA RSS images
```

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positional arguments:

RSS RSS images to process

options:

-h, --help show this help message and exit

--wcs-grid, --display-wcs-grid
Display WCS grid

--wcs-pa-from-header Use PA angle from PC keys

--fix-missing Interpolate missing fibers

--average-region AVERAGE_REGION AVERAGE_REGION
Region of the RSS averaged on display

--extname EXTNAME, -e EXTNAME
Name of the extension used

--column COLUMN, -c COLUMN
Column of the RSS on display

--continuum-region CONTINUUM_REGION CONTINUUM_REGION
Region of the RSS used for continuum subtraction

--coordinate-type {pixel,wcs}
Types of coordinates used

--colormap COLORMAP Name of a valid matplotlib colormap

--plot-sky, --display-sky
Display SKY bundles

--display-fibid, --plot-fibid
Display fiber IDs of the spaxels

--plot-nominal-config
Plot nominal configuration, do not use the header

--hide-values Do not show values out of range

--title TITLE Title of the plot

--label LABEL Legend of the colorbar

--hex-size HEX_SIZE Size of the hexagons (default is 0.443)

--hex-rel-size HEX_REL_SIZE
Scale the size of hexagons by a factor

--min-cut MIN_CUT Inferior cut level

--max-cut MAX_CUT Superior cut level

--percent PERCENT Compute cuts using percentiles

--stretch {linear,sqrt,power,log,asinh}
Name of the stretch method used for display

contouring:

--contour-pixel-size CONTOUR_PIXEL_SIZE
Pixel size in arc seconds for image reconstruction

--contour-levels CONTOUR_LEVELS
Contour levels

--contour Draw contours

--contour-image CONTOUR_IMAGE
Image for computing contours

--contour-image-column CONTOUR_IMAGE_COLUMN
Column of image used for contouring

--contour-image-save CONTOUR_IMAGE_SAVE
Save image used for contouring

--contour-image-region CONTOUR_IMAGE_REGION CONTOUR_IMAGE_REGION
Region of the image used for contouring

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```
--contour-is-density The data is a magnitude that does not require scaling
```

Note that this visualization tool can be also used to display output RSS files from the `analyze_rss.py` tool described below. As an example, the command to display the flux the first of the two gaussians fit to a specific emission line analyzed with that code would be (see Section 6.8):

```
(megara) $ python -m megaradrp.visualization \
    test/analyze_rss_Halpha.fits -c 22 --min-cut 10. --max-cut 400.
```

7.3 Megaradrp-Cube

This tool allows to convert the output RSS file from the MegaraLcbImage recipe (with or without the sky spectrum subtracted) into a FITS datacube (x,y,z) where the z axis corresponds to every lambda in the input RSS file and the (x,y) axes correspond to the two coordinates in the sky (RA & Dec if instrument PA is 0°). Since this tool is now part of the MEGARA DRP it should be run from within the DRP environment by doing:

```
(megara) $ megaradrp-cube -h
usage: convert_rss_cube [-h] [-p PIXEL_SIZE] [-o OUTFILE] [-d]
                        [-m {nn,linear}] [--wcs-pa-from-header]
                        [--fix-missing]
                        rss

positional arguments:
  rss                    RSS file with fiber traces

options:
  -h, --help            show this help message and exit
  -p PIXEL_SIZE, --pixel-size PIXEL_SIZE
                        Pixel size in arc seconds
  -o OUTFILE, --outfile OUTFILE
                        Name of the output cube file
  -d, --disable-scaling
                        Disable flux conservation
  -m {nn,linear}, --method {nn,linear}
                        Method of interpolation
  --wcs-pa-from-header  Use PA angle from header
  --fix-missing         Interpolate missing fibers
```

Default parameters for the `--disable-scaling` and `--wcs-pa-from-header` options should be fine for regular MEGARA data processed with the DRP.

An alternative software with similar scope has been developed by Javier Zaragoza Cardiel (from INAOE) and can be obtained through GitHub at <https://github.com/javierzaragoza/megararss2cube>.

7.4 Extract spectrum: megaratools-extract_spectrum

This tool is the first being described in this cookbook that is part of the **megaratools** package available through GitHub at <https://github.com/guaix-ucm/megara-tools>. The objective of this tool is to generate an extracted (1D) spectrum of a given fiber or set of fibers. The main parameter determining the fiber(s) to be extracted is the fiber number as measured in the pseudo-slit (from 1 to 623 in the case of the LCB; 1 to 644 for the MOS). Since the RSS products of the **MegaraMosImage** recipe already include an extension with the 7 fibers of the each minibundle added together, this is particularly useful for extracting spectra of different regions from processed LCB RSS frames. The resulting extracted spectrum shares wavelength calibration solution with the RSS. All tools included in the **megaratools** package can be called as an argument for the Python main interpreter or as executables on their own, although the latter option is recommended:

```
(megara) $ python <path_to_extract_spectrum>/extract_spectrum.py -h
```

```
(megara) $ megaratools-extract_spectrum -h
```

The result of the task when called using the help (-h) argument is:

```
usage: extract_spectrum [-h] [-s RSS-SPECTRUM] [-t INPUT-TABLE] [-c COLUMN]
                        [-g GREP-STRING] [-o OUTPUT-SPECTRUM] [-p]
```

Extract spectrum based on fiber IDs

options:

```
-h, --help                show this help message and exit
-s RSS-SPECTRUM, --spectrum RSS-SPECTRUM
                        RSS FITS spectrum
-t INPUT-TABLE, --ids-table INPUT-TABLE
                        File with list of IDs
-c COLUMN, --column COLUMN
                        Column to select from table
-g GREP-STRING, --grep-string GREP-STRING
                        String to do grep in table
-o OUTPUT-SPECTRUM, --output OUTPUT-SPECTRUM
                        Output 1D spectrum
-p, --plot                Plot spectrum instead?
```

The table with the fiber ids (-t) is a simple ASCII file in which one of the (space-separated) columns is the fiber id. The user can also choose a set of rows that fulfils the condition of including a specific string (using -g). An example of a file like this could be:

```
(megara) $ cat test/regions.fibers
```

```
Region1 321
Region1 319
Region2 454
Region2 460
Region2 474
```

Should be the user be interested in extracting the fibers corresponding to Region #2 (fibers 454, 460 & 474) from `final_rss.fits` file in the `test/` directory to a `Region2.fits` file, he/she can simply run:

```
(megara) $ megaratools-extract_spectrum -s test/final_rss.fits \
-t test/regions.fibers -c 2 -g Region2 -o test/Region2.fits
```

The user can also decide to visualize the extracted spectrum without saving it as a new FITS file. In that case he/she should make use of the `-p` option:

```
(megara) $ megaratools-extract_spectrum -s test/final_rss.fits \  
-t test/regions.fibers -c 2 -g Region2 -p
```


One of the uses of this tool is to extract the spectrum of the (flux-calibrated) `final_rss.fits` of a standard star processed with `MegaraLcbImage` to verify that it matches the corresponding tabulated spectrum. This extraction can be done using the `fiber_ids.txt` file that it is stored in the `*_results/` directory generated by the MEGARA DRP when running this recipe. In the case the command would read (using two single quotes for the `-g` option we ensure that the command selects all rows extraction):

```
(megara) $ megaratools-extract_spectrum -s test/final_rss.fits \  
-t test/fiber_ids.txt -c 1 -g '' -p
```


7.5 Extract elliptical apertures: megaratools-extract_rings

This tool (also part of **megara-tools**) is similar to the previous one but allows to automatically extract spectra of elliptical rings or arbitrary size, orientation and ellipticity around a given position (fiber). This is particularly useful of the analysis the radial variation of properties derived from RSS data when the signal-to-noise ratio does not allow to carry out a spaxel-by-spaxel analysis. The options for this command are:

```
(megara) $ megaratools-extract_rings -h
usage: extract_elliptical_rings_spectrum [-h] [-r RSS-SPECTRUM] [-a] [-b]
                                         [-c CENTRAL-FIBER] [-n NUMBER-RINGS]
                                         [-w RINGS WIDTH] [-s SAVED-RSS]
                                         [-e ELLIPTICITY] [-pa POSITION ANGLE]
                                         [-v]
```

Extract spectra based on elliptical rings

options:

```
-h, --help                show this help message and exit
-r RSS-SPECTRUM, --rss RSS-SPECTRUM
                          RSS FITS spectrum
-a, --accumulate
-b, --surface_brightness
-c CENTRAL-FIBER, --central-fiber CENTRAL-FIBER
                          Central fiber
-n NUMBER-RINGS, --number-rings NUMBER-RINGS
                          Number of rings
-w RINGS WIDTH, --width RINGS WIDTH
                          Elliptical rings width (arcsec)
-s SAVED-RSS, --saved-rss SAVED-RSS
                          Output RSS file
```

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```
-e ELLIPTICITY, --ellipticity ELLIPTICITY
                        Elliptical rings ellipticity
-pa POSITION ANGLE, --position-angle POSITION ANGLE
                        Elliptical rings position angle (N->E)
-v, --verbose
```

The command creates an RSS file with the same wavelength calibration solution as the input RSS file but a number of columns equal to the number of rings extracted (as set by the `-n` option). Besides, this command when run with the verbose option (`-v`) on it also outputs the main parameters of the rings extracted: average surface brightness at the central wavelength (in Jy/spx or Jy/arcsec² if the `-b` option is set) and area. Below, we show an example of how this command is run and of the output it creates in verbose mode.

```
(megara) $ megaratools-extract_rings -r test/final_rss.fits -c 311 \
        -b -w 0.6 -n 5 -s test/rings.fits -e 0.8 -pa 0. -v

Ring #1: 0.010272977933 Jy/[asec/spx]^2 (@CWL) - area/rad: 1.1618385/0.3 [asec/spx]^2/
→asec)
Ring #2: 0.006704834831 Jy/[asec/spx]^2 (@CWL) - area/rad: 3.3284848/0.9 [asec/spx]^2/
→asec)
Ring #3: 0.002757987470 Jy/[asec/spx]^2 (@CWL) - area/rad: 4.1630143/1.5 [asec/spx]^2/
→asec)
Ring #4: 0.001841463727 Jy/[asec/spx]^2 (@CWL) - area/rad: 6.5997403/2.1 [asec/spx]^2/
→asec)
Ring #5: 0.001480577862 Jy/[asec/spx]^2 (@CWL) - area/rad: 9.4244147/2.7 [asec/spx]^2/
→asec)
```

Note that this tool can be also used to add the fluxes within (complete) elliptical apertures, not only rings by using the `-a` option. The resulting RSS can be used to extract the spectra of each ring/aperture by combining its use with the `megaratools-extract_spectrum` tool described in Section [Extract spectrum: megaratools-extract_spectrum](#). Examples of that use are:

```
(megara) $ megaratools-extract_spectrum -s test/final_rss.fits \
        -t test/rings.dat -c 1 -g 1 -o test/ring1.fits
(megara) $ megaratools-extract_spectrum -s test/final_rss.fits \
        -t test/rings.dat -c 1 -g 2 -o test/ring2.fits
...
```

where the `test/rings.dat` file is simply a list of integer numbers.

7.6 Plot spectrum: megaratools-plot_spectrum

This tool allows to plot a 1D MEGARA spectrum. It also allows to combine the spectrum plotted with a tabulated spectrum (e.g. that from a standard star) and a list of spectral lines. The options that can be used for the `megaratools-plot_spectrum` tool are:

```
(megara) $ megaratools-plot_spectrum -h
usage: plot_spectrum [-h] [-s SPECTRUM/FILE_LIST] [-l] [-t STD-TABLE]
                    [-c LINECAT-TABLE] [-z LINECAT-Z] [-o OUTPUT-PDF] [-e]
                    [-p] [-n] [-L1 INITIAL LAMBDA] [-L2 LAST LAMBDA]
                    [-F1 YMIN FLUX] [-F2 YMAX FLUX] [-T PLOT TITLE]
```

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Input spectrum and table

options:

```

-h, --help          show this help message and exit
-s SPECTRUM/FILE_LIST, --spectrum SPECTRUM/FILE_LIST
                    FITS spectrum / list of FITS spectra
-l, --is-a-list     Use for -s being a list of FITS spectra
-t STD-TABLE, --std-table STD-TABLE
                    Standard-star spectrum table
-c LINECAT-TABLE, --catalog LINECAT-TABLE
                    Cataloged lines CSV table
-z LINECAT-Z, --redshift LINECAT-Z
                    Redshift for catalog lines
-o OUTPUT-PDF, --output OUTPUT-PDF
                    Output PDF
-e, --efficiency    Efficiency?
-p, --plot          Plot spectrum?
-n, --no-legend     Legend?
-L1 INITIAL LAMBDA, --min-lambda INITIAL LAMBDA
                    Initial (rest-frame) lambda to plot
-L2 LAST LAMBDA, --max-lambda LAST LAMBDA
                    Last (rest-frame) lambda to plot
-F1 YMIN FLUX, --min-flambda YMIN FLUX
                    Minimum flux to plot
-F2 YMAX FLUX, --max-flambda YMAX FLUX
                    Maximum flux to plot
-T PLOT TITLE, --title PLOT TITLE
                    Title of the plot

```

Below we show an example of its use and the resulting plot (**Figure 19**).

```

(megara) $ megaratools-plot_spectrum -s test/spectrum.fits \
-t test/mbd33d2642.dat -p -T 'BD+33 2642 spectrum' \
-L1 6000 -L2 7500 -F1 2E-14 -F2 2E-13 -c test/bright_lines.dat

```


Figure 19: Result of the `megaratoools-plot_spectrum` of standard star BD+33 2642 along with the CALSPEC tabulated spectrum and a series of spectral lines at the recession velocity of the source.

The tabulated spectrum is assumed to be in AB magnitudes and the file with a catalogue of spectral lines must have the following format:

```
(megara) $ cat test/bright_lines.dat
[N II],6548.1
Ha,6562.8
[N II],6583.4
[S II],6716.3
[S II],6730.7
```

Along with the input spectrum, `megaratoools-plot_spectrum` also shows (see **Figure 19**) the wavelength limits corresponding to the spectral range that is common to all fibers (cyan lines) and that where the computation (smoothing) of the sensitivity curve yields a reliable flux calibration (dashed red lines). In that regard, it is also worth noting that this tool can be also used to plot efficiency curves generated by the `LcbStdStar` recipe (e.g. `master_sensitivity.fits`), as shown in **Figure 14**, both in their nominal units (electrons/Jy) or in relative efficiency (when the option `-e` is used) assuming 80% pupil losses and 80% telescope efficiency relative to its effective area.

7.7 Diffuse light determination: `megaratoools-diffuse_light`

In some MEGARA observations taken under bright moon conditions during 2018 and 2019 some reflected moonlight did manage to reach the spectrograph camera and the detector. This diffuse light appeared as a low-frequency pattern that could amount from just a few to tens of counts (see top-left panel of **Figure 20**). This tool fits this pattern using information from the region of the CCD that is not illuminated by the fibers below and above the pseudo-slit and in between the boxes that constitute it. **Figure 21** shows the result of the fit of an average of 50 columns to a 4th-order polynomial to the flux of regions illuminated by diffuse light alone.

Figure 20: Example of an image with diffuse light contamination (top-left panel). The residuals after the best fit in 2D is performed is shown in the top-right panel. Low-frequency background models obtained by fitting only columns (left) and in 2D (columns first, then columns) (right) are in the bottom panels.

Below we show how this tool is executed and some basic information on its different options.

```
(megara) $ megaratoools-diffuse_light -h
usage: clean_diffuse_light [-h] [-i INPUT-IMAGE] [-o OUTPUT-IMAGE]
                        [-r RESIDUALS-IMAGE] [-t MASTER-TRACES]
                        [-s SHIFT-TRACES] [-w SEARCH-WINDOW]
                        [-d DEGREE-POLY-COLS] [-d2 DEGREE-POLY-ROWS]
                        [-p OUTPUT-PLOT] [-b SPECTRAL-BINNING]
                        [-e EXCLUDE-REGION [EXCLUDE-REGION ...]] [-2D]
```

Cleaning of diffuse light from a reduced (non-RSS) MEGARA image

options:

```
-h, --help          show this help message and exit
-i INPUT-IMAGE, --input INPUT-IMAGE
                    Reduced FITS image
-o OUTPUT-IMAGE, --output OUTPUT-IMAGE
                    Output diffuse-light FITS image
-r RESIDUALS-IMAGE, --residuals RESIDUALS-IMAGE
                    Output residual FITS image
-t MASTER-TRACES, --traces MASTER-TRACES
                    Master traces JSON file
-s SHIFT-TRACES, --shift SHIFT-TRACES
                    Traces shift
-w SEARCH-WINDOW, --window SEARCH-WINDOW
                    Window around traces to search for non-illuminated
                    fibers
-d DEGREE-POLY-COLS, --degree DEGREE-POLY-COLS
                    Degree of polynomial fit for columns
```

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```

-d2 DEGREE-POLY-ROWS, --degree-rows DEGREE-POLY-ROWS
    Degree of polynomial fit for rows
-p OUTPUT-PLOT, --outplot OUTPUT-PLOT
    Output plots
-b SPECTRAL-BINNING, --binning SPECTRAL-BINNING
    Binning in the spectral direction
-e EXCLUDE-REGION [EXCLUDE-REGION ...], --exclude EXCLUDE-REGION [EXCLUDE-REGION ...]
    Exclude region (c1 c2 r1 r2), e.g. 2407 2720 0 164
-2D, --two-dimensional
    Two-dimensional fitting?

```

Most of these options are related to the different fitting parameters used. Note that the input image should be the `reduced_image.fits` image generated by, among others, the **MegaraLcbImage** and **MegaraMosImage** recipes, that is place in the corresponding `*_work/` directory. This cannot be run on raw images as those have different bias levels and gains for its two amplifiers. A master-traces file and the offset between them and the position of the fibers in the contaminated image should be provided as well (options `-t` and `-s`, respectively).

Figure 21: Fit to the sum of 50 columns (left) and 50 rows (right) for a `reduced_image.fits` contaminated by diffuse light. The 2D fit ensures that potential bright lines (peak in the right-panel profile) do not significantly affect the modeling results. Black points correspond to those pixels used to perform this fit. A fourth-order polynomial was used in these fits.

Option `-e` (defined in pixels) allows to exclude a specific region from the fit (white rectangle in top-right panel of **Figure 20**). This is particularly useful from some very early observations in the red (LR-R, MR-R, MR-RI) in which light from the pseudo-slit mechanism LED was adding some diffuse light just below the position of the spectra on the CCD but not the under the light from the fibers itself, making this region not useful to fit any low-frequency pattern present throughout the entire CCD. An example of the use of this tool follows:

```

(megara) $ megaratools-diffuse_light -i test/reduced_image.fits \
-o test/background_2D.fits -r test/residuals_2D.fits \
-t test/master_traces.json -s 1.2 -p test/plots_2D.pdf \
-e 2407 2720 0 154 -2D

```

The result of this command is a low-frequency background image (the one set by the `-o` option). See the bottom panels of **Figure 20** in this regard, for the best fit along columns only (left panel) and fitting the result also along rows (right panel). In order to remove this image during the data processing with the DRP, both the **MegaraLcbImage** and

MegaraMosImage count with a requirement called `diffuse_light_image` that should be set to the image resulting from this tool. That image should be placed under the `data/*` directory where the **megaradrp** is being run. This requirement is added in the development versions of the **megaradrp** or in Python package versions released after July 1st 2020 (**numina** and **megaradrp** versions 0.22+ and 0.10+, respectively). The user can find more info on the set of requirements of these tasks by doing:

```
(megara) $ numina show-recipes -m MegaraLcbImage
```

This tool also generates a clean image that, although of no use within the **megaradrp**, can be used to verify the quality of the low-frequency background modeling performed (see bottom panel of **Figure 20**). Output background images generated by `megaratools-diffuse_light` have keyword NUM-DFL added to their headers.

7.8 Analysis of a 1D emission-line spectrum: `megaratools-analyze_spectrum`

There are multiple tools that perform the analysis of spectral of astronomical sources, both the stellar continuum and emission lines (pPXF, Steckmap, Fit3D, FADO, to name a few). However, most of these software tools do not work right away on data from a new instrument, although many started from the need of analyzing data from a specific spectrograph and survey, such as SAURON (pPXF) or PPaK/CALIFA (Fit3D). In the case of MEGARA three different tools are used, one that is based on pPXF (see e.g. [Dullo et al. 2019](#); not yet public) and two that are designed for the analysis of single emission lines on extracted 1D (`megaratools-analyze_spectrum`, below) and RSS 2D MEGARA spectra (`megaratools-analyze_rss`, Section 6.8).

The `megaratools-analyze_spectrum` tool allows to determine all parameters of a specific emission lines by fitting different functions (linear continuum plus a modelled single gaussian, double gaussian or Gauss-Hermite polynomials to a single emission line) within a given spectral range. As this tool is used on extracted 1D spectrum, the output is given on the screen and no output file is created. This tool is executed by doing:

```
(megara) $ megaratools-analyze_spectrum -h
usage: analyze_spectrum [-h] [-s SPECTRUM/FILE_LIST] [-l]
                        [-f FITTING FUNCTION (0,1,2)]
                        [-w LINE CENTRAL WAVELENGTH] [-k]
                        [-LW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - LINE]
                        [-LW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - LINE]
                        [-CW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - CONT]
                        [-CW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - CONT]
                        [-ECW1 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (LOWER WAVELENGTH)]
                        [-ECW2 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (UPPER WAVELENGTH)]
                        [-PW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - PLOT]
                        [-PW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - PLOT]
                        [-S2 SCALE FACTOR FOR AMP2] [-t SPEC-TABLE]
                        [-c LINECAT-TABLE] [-z REDSHIFT] [-o OUTPUT-PDF] [-p]
                        [-n]
```

ANALYZE SPECTRUM

options:

```
-h, --help          show this help message and exit
-s SPECTRUM/FILE_LIST, --spectrum SPECTRUM/FILE_LIST
                    FITS spectrum / list of FITS spectra
-l, --is-a-list     Use for -s being a list of FITS spectra
-f FITTING FUNCTION (0,1,2), --method FITTING FUNCTION (0,1,2)
```

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```

        Fitting function (0=gauss_hermite, 1=gauss,
        2=double_gauss)
-w LINE CENTRAL WAVELENGTH, --ctwl LINE CENTRAL WAVELENGTH
        Central rest-frame wavelength for line (AA)
-k, --use-peak          Use peak first guess on central wavelength
-LW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - LINE, --lcut1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - LINE
        Lower rest-frame wavelength for line (AA)
-LW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - LINE, --lcut2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - LINE
        Upper rest-frame wavelength for line (AA)
-CW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - CONT, --ccut1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - CONT
        Lower rest-frame wavelength for cont. (AA)
-CW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - CONT, --ccut2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - CONT
        Upper rest-frame wavelength for cont. (AA)
-ECW1 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (LOWER WAVELENGTH), --eccut1 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (LOWER_
↪WAVELENGTH)
        Lower rest-frame wavelength of range to exclude for
        cont. (AA)
-ECW2 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (UPPER WAVELENGTH), --eccut2 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (UPPER_
↪WAVELENGTH)
        Upper rest-frame wavelength of range to exclude for
        cont. (AA)
-PW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - PLOT, --pcut1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - PLOT
        Lower rest-frame wavelength for plot (AA)
-PW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - PLOT, --pcut2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - PLOT
        Upper rest-frame wavelength for plot (AA)
-S2 SCALE FACTOR FOR AMP2, --scale-amp2 SCALE FACTOR FOR AMP2
        Scale factor for amplitude 2
-t SPEC-TABLE, --spec-table SPEC-TABLE
        Additional spectrum table
-c LINECAT-TABLE, --catalog LINECAT-TABLE
        Cataloged lines CSV table
-z REDSHIFT, --redshift REDSHIFT
        Redshift for target and catalog lines
-o OUTPUT-PDF, --output OUTPUT-PDF
        Output PDF
-p, --plot              Plot spectrum?
-n, --no-legend         Legend?

```

Some of the options of this task are common to the ones in `megaratoools_plot_spectrum`, including the possibility of adding a tabulated spectrum (-t) or catalog of spectral lines (-c), defining the redshift of the source (-z), creating an output PDF (-o) with or without legend (-n). Here we show an example of its usage:

```

(megara) $ megaratoools-analyze_spectrum -s test/spectrum.fits \
        -f 2 -w 6563 -LW1 6552 -LW2 6570 -CW1 6400 -CW2 6710 \
        -ECW1 6545 -ECW2 6588 -PW1 6350 -PW2 6800 -f 2 \
        -c test/bright_lines.dat -p -k -z "-0.00025" -S2 " -0.2"

```

Note that setting values to -LW1, -LW2, -CW1, -CW2, -PW1, -PW2 is mandatory. The tool, based on some of the options introduced, determines an initial set of fitting parameters. If the -k option is set, the initial guess on the line peak is taken from the maximum value (after the best-fitting continuum is removed) within the specified fitting range. For the initial guesses on the 1st and 2nd-order moments we take the position of that maximum and some factor (~1-1.2, depending on the model function; see below) of the instrumental FWHM. The models considered to date are:

- Gauss-Hermite polynomials (-f 0)
- Single gaussian (-f 1)
- Two gaussians (-f 2)

In the case of the model with two gaussians one can scale the initial guess on the peak intensity of the second gaussian relative to the first one. This is particularly useful when underlying absorption is present in the spectral range of the fit (see **Figure 22**). After executing this command, it prints in the screen both the input and output (best-fitting) parameters. The content of this output also depends on the type of model function chosen to fit the emission line. The output of the example above would be the following:

```
FITTING CONTINUUM:
Input(slope,yord):  0.000E+00  9.724E-14
Output(slope,yord): -5.336E-17  4.468E-13
Best-fitting chisqr continuum:  7.321E-27
BASIC NUMBERS:
(mean,rms,lpk,pk,S/N) 9.682864107165422e-14  2.9143067925725397e-15  6561.03  1.
↪658473599169167e-13  56.907996213575935
FITTING METHOD: DOUBLE GAUSSIAN
Input(i1,l1,sig1,i2,l2,sig2):  6.212E-14  6561.03  0.47  -1.380E-15  6561.03  0.93
Flux1 from model:  8.224E-14+/-  9.845E-15
Flux2 from model:  -1.117E-13+/-  9.573E-15
Output(i1,l1,sig1,i2,l2,sig2):  8.308E-14  6561.11  0.39  -1.263E-14  6561.31  3.63
Flux & EW from data:  -2.844E-14+/-  9.690E-15  -0.29+/-  0.10
Flux & EW from model:  -2.949E-14+/-  9.689E-15  -0.30+/-  0.10
Best-fitting chisqr:  2.279E-28
```

Note that the term `from data` refers to the sum of the flux above the continuum within the spectral range used to fit the line profile, while the term `from model` refers to the analytic integral of the model.

Besides, `megaratools-analyze_spectrum` displays a plot (similar to the ones shown in **Figure 22**) that includes:

- The input spectrum in the range set by options `-PW` `1` and `` ` -PW2` (blue line)
- Vertical lines of the different spectral ranges of interest, including the range covered by all fibers (cyan line) and with precise flux calibration in the original RSS frame (dashed red line), the range for fitting the continuum (dashed grey lines) and that where the line fit is performed (solid gray line).
- Best-fitting continuum (solid red line).
- Best-fitting line plus continuum (solid orange line).

The user should check the ranges chosen and then kill the graphical terminal for the code to start running.

Figure 22: Two different views of the plot generated by `megaratools-analyze_spectrum` for the example given in the text. In this case the line fitted is $H\alpha$ and the method used was a double gaussian, where the intensity of the secondary gaussian was set to negative 20% of the intensity of the primary one to model the underlying absorption in this (Balmer) line.

7.9 Analysis of a 2D RSS emission-line spectrum: `megaratools-analyze_rss`

Based on the fitting procedure of `megaratools-analyze_spectrum` tool we also developed a tool that is able to do the same spectral analysis in MEGARA RSS files. This is particularly useful for creating maps of derived properties (fluxes, line-of-sight radial velocity and velocity dispersion and higher-order momenta) from the analysis of LCB RSS final data (`final_rss.fits` or `reduced_rss.fits` files created by the `MegaraLcbImage` recipe).

The tool is called `megaratools-analyze_rss` and it is executed by doing:

```
(megara) $ megaratools-analyze_rss -h
usage: analyze_rss [-h] [-s RSS FILE] [-f FITTING FUNCTION (0,1,2)]
                  [-S MINIMUM S/N] [-w LINE CENTRAL WAVELENGTH] [-k]
                  [-LW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - LINE]
                  [-LW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - LINE]
                  [-CW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - CONT]
                  [-CW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - CONT]
                  [-ECW1 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (LOWER WAVELENGTH)]
                  [-ECW2 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (UPPER WAVELENGTH)]
                  [-PW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - PLOT]
                  [-PW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - PLOT] [-S2 SCALE FACTOR FOR AMP2]
                  [-z REDSHIFT] [-o OUTPUT-PDF] [-v] [-O OUTPUT RSS FILE]
                  [-of OUTPUT FIBERS LIST]

----- ANALYZE_RSS PROGRAM -----

----- OUTPUT PARAMETER IN OUTPUT FITS -----
Property channel description

... FM          # 0 Fitting method (0=gauss-hermite,1=1gauss,2=2gauss)
... CONTINUUM  # 1 Continuum level in cgs
```

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```

... NOISE      # 2 rms in cgs
... SNR       # 3 S/N at the peak of the line
... FLUXD     # 4 Flux from window_data - window_continuum
... EWD       # 5 Flux from window_data - window_continuum / mean_continuum
... FLUXF     # 6 Flux from best-fitting function(s)
... EWF       # 7 EW from best-fitting function(s)
... H0        # 8 amplitude for methods 0 & 1 & 2 (first gaussian)
... H1        # 9 central lambda for methods 0 & 1 & 2 (first gaussian)
... H2        # 10 sigma (in AA) for methods 0 & 1 & 2 (first gaussian)
... H3        # 11 h3 for method 0
... H4        # 12 h4 for method 0
... H0B       # 13 amplitude for method 2 (second gaussian)
... H1B       # 14 central lambda for method 2 (second gaussian)
... H2B       # 15 sigma (in AA) for method 2 (second gaussian)
... H1KS      # 16 velocity in km/s from H1 (1st g)
... H2KS      # 17 sigma in km/s from H2 (1st g)
... H2KLC     # 18 sigma in km/s from H2 corrected for instrumental sigma (1st g)
... H1KSB     # 19 velocity in km/s from H1B (2nd g)
... H2KSB     # 20 sigma in km/s from H2B (2nd g)
... H2KLCB    # 21 sigma in km/s from H2 corrected for instrumental sigma (2nd g)
... FLUXF1    # 22 Flux from best-fitting 1st gaussian
... FLUXF2    # 23 Flux from best-fitting 2nd gaussian
... EFLUXD    # 24 Error of 4 (Flux from window_data - window_continuum)
... EEWD      # 25 Error of 5 (Flux from window_data - window_continuum / mean_
↳continuum)
... EFLUXF    # 26 Error of 6 (Flux from best-fitting function(s))
... EEWF      # 27 Error of 7 (EW from best-fitting function(s))
... CHI2      # 28 best-fitting chi^2 (cgs)

```

options:

```

-h, --help          show this help message and exit
-s RSS FILE, --spectrum RSS FILE
                    RSS input file
-f FITTING FUNCTION (0,1,2), --method FITTING FUNCTION (0,1,2)
                    Fitting function (0=gauss_hermite, 1=gauss, 2=double_gauss)
-S MINIMUM S/N, --limsnr MINIMUM S/N
                    Mininum Signal-to-noise ratio in each spaxel
-w LINE CENTRAL WAVELENGTH, --ctwl LINE CENTRAL WAVELENGTH
                    Central rest-frame wavelength for line (AA)
-k, --use-peak      Use peak first guess on central wavelength
-LW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - LINE, --lcut1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - LINE
                    Lower rest-frame wavelength for line (AA)
-LW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - LINE, --lcut2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - LINE
                    Upper rest-frame wavelength for line (AA)
-CW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - CONT, --ccut1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - CONT
                    Lower rest-frame wavelength for cont. (AA)
-CW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - CONT, --ccut2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - CONT
                    Upper rest-frame wavelength for cont. (AA)
-ECW1 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (LOWER WAVELENGTH), --eccut1 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (LOWER_
↳WAVELENGTH)
                    Lower rest-frame wavelength of range to exclude for cont. (AA)
-ECW2 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (UPPER WAVELENGTH), --eccut2 EXCLUDE FROM CONT. (UPPER_

```

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```

→WAVELENGTH)
    Upper rest-frame wavelength of range to exclude for cont. (AA)
-PW1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - PLOT, --pcut1 LOWER WAVELENGTH - PLOT
    Lower (observed) wavelength for plot (AA)
-PW2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - PLOT, --pcut2 UPPER WAVELENGTH - PLOT
    Upper (observed) wavelength for plot (AA)
-S2 SCALE FACTOR FOR AMP2, --scale-amp2 SCALE FACTOR FOR AMP2
    Scale factor for amplitude 2
-z REDSHIFT, --redshift REDSHIFT
    Redshift for target and catalog lines
-o OUTPUT-PDF, --output OUTPUT-PDF
    Output PDF
-v, --verbose
    Verbose mode for fitting results?
-O OUTPUT RSS FILE, --output-rss OUTPUT RSS FILE
    Output RSS file
-of OUTPUT FIBERS LIST, --output-fibers OUTPUT FIBERS LIST
    Output list of fibers above minimum Signal-to-noise ratio

```

Although the spectral ranges and model function set by the options of the parameter are common to all fibers, option `-S` allows to set a minimum signal-to-noise ratio for the peak intensity below which no fit is attempted. The verbose mode allows to print to screen the same output results as those shown by default by the `megarertools-analyze_spectrum` tool but for each individual fiber fulfilling the minimum S/N criteria imposed.

The rest of the options are identical to the ones described for the `megarertools-analysis_spectrum` tool. The main difference comes from the output products. While in the case of the `megarertools-analysis_spectrum` tool only printed output is produced, this tool generates an RSS FITS file of products that has the same number of rows as the input RSS (623 or 644) but only 29 columns, one per derived property, including the majority of the model best-fitting parameters. The properties included in columns 0 to 28 of the output RSS and their meaning are listed above as part of the online help information provided by the tool (`-h` option). The output also includes a PDF file with the graphical result of all fibers that were fit (plots with the original spectra of fibers with S/N below the number given in option `-S` are also included) and an ascii file listing the ids of the fibers that matched our minimum S/N requirement. This file is useful as it can be used (in combination with `megarertools-extract_spectrum`) to generate a high-S/N emission-line spectrum of our target. **Figure 23** shows the plots generated for two specific fibers and two different spectral lines using the instructions given later in this section.

Below we provide two examples of the execution of the `megarertools-analyzed_rss` tool for two different spectral lines in the same spectral setup: $H\alpha$ and $[NII]\lambda 6584$. Right after each of these commands is executed, the program shows a plot of the integrated spectrum (all fiber spectra added up) with all relevant spectral ranges clearly identified with vertical lines. The RSS product files generated by these two instructions will be later used to compute an RSS file that can be used to create a line-ratio map.

```

(megara) $ megarertools-analyze_rss -s test/final_rss.fits -f 2 \
-w 6563 -LW1 6552 -LW2 6570 -CW1 6400 -CW2 6710 \
-ECW1 6545. -ECW2 6588 -PW1 6350 -PW2 6800 -f 2 -k \
-z "-0.00025" -S2 " -0.2" -S 5 \
-o test/analyze_rss_Halpha.pdf \
-O test/analyze_rss_Halpha.fits \
-of test/analyze_rss_Halpha.fibers

(megara) $ megarertools-analyze_rss -s test/final_rss.fits -f 2 \
-w 6584 -LW1 6580 -LW2 6587 -CW1 6400 -CW2 6710 \
-ECW1 6545. -ECW2 6588 -PW1 6350 -PW2 6800 -f 1 -k \
-z "-0.00025" -S 5 \

```

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```
-o test/analyze_rss_N2.pdf \
-O test/analyze_rss_N2.fits \
-of test/analyze_rss_N2.fibers
```


Figure 23: Results of the fitting of $H\alpha$ (left panel) and $[NII]\lambda 6584$ (right panel) spectral lines for fibers 291 and 321, respectively. As for the graphical output of `megaratools-analyze_spectrum`, the input spectrum is shown in blue, the range used for the fitting the continuum is bracketed between dashed grey lines, the range for fitting the line in between solid grey lines, the best-fitting continuum is shown as a solid red line and the best-fitting line plus continuum is in orange.

7.10 RSS arithmetics: `megaratools-rss_arith`

The tool `megaratools-rss_arith` described here allows to perform basic computations (Python basic arithmetic and `numpy` numerical operations) on RSS files. The online help output is shown below.

```
(megara) $ megaratools-rss_arith -h
usage: combine_rss [-h] [-e Equation to evaluate] [-o OUTPUT RSS] rss

Combining by averaging aligned RSS files

positional arguments:
  rss                  Input table with list of RSS files

options:
  -h, --help          show this help message and exit
  -e Equation to evaluate, --equation Equation to evaluate
                       Example: '(ima1[:,9] + ima2[:,10])/ ima3[:,3]'
  -o OUTPUT RSS, --output OUTPUT RSS
                       Output RSS
```

The input of this tool is a text file with the list of images involved in the operation (all of the same size):

```
(megara) $ cat test/images.txt
test/analyze_rss_N2.fits
```

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```
test/analyze_rss_Halpha.fits
test/final_rss.fits
```

The output is always an RSS file with one single column and the same number of rows as the input images. The philosophy behind of this tool is rather similar to that of the **imexpr** command in IRAF.

The tool can be used for multiple purposes using any of the **numpy** array operations. Below we show examples of some potential usages of `megaratoos-rss_arith`. For example:

```
(megara) $ megaratoos-rss_arith test/images.txt \
-e 'np.log10(ima1[:,6]/ima2[:,22])' \
-o test/logN2_over_Ha_rss.fits
```

This instruction includes the options required to create a line-ratio RSS (in log10 scale) from two RSS FITS files created by the `megaratoos-analyze_rss` tool for the $H\alpha$ and $[NII\lambda 6584]$ lines. Note that, given that we are using only the flux of the emission component of $H\alpha$, we use channel #22, which corresponds to the line flux of only the primary gaussian (see description of tool `megaratoos-analyze_rss` in Section 6.8), for $H\alpha$ and channel #6 for $[NII\lambda 6584]$.

Other examples are:

```
(megara) $ megaratoos-rss_arith test/images.txt \
-e '(np.mean(ima3[:,1000:2000],axis=1))' \
-o test/mean_1000_2000.fits

(megara) $ megaratoos-rss_arith test/images.txt \
-e '(np.mean(ima3[:,2000:3000],axis=1))' \
-o test/mean_2000_3000.fits
```

In these cases, we compute the mean of all the flux from spectral pixels 1000 to 2000 (top) and 2000 to 3000 (bottom) to create two new separated RSS files. We can now create a spectral-index-like RSS image by running:

```
(megara) $ megaratoos-rss_arith test/images2.txt \
-e 'ima4[:,0]/ima5[:,0]' -o test/index.fits
```

The user should bear in mind that `test/images2.txt` now includes two additional rows with the names of the images created above: `test/mean_1000_2000.fits` and `test/mean_2000_3000.fits`. Note that although the images listed in the `test/images2.txt` file would have different dimensions we would not get any error because (1) they have the same number of rows (623 in this case) and (2) images of different dimensions are not combined in the same execution of `megaratoos-rss_arith`. We show in **Figure 24** the resulting `test/index.fits` RSS image using the `megaradrp.visualization` tool described in Section 6.1. This figure was obtained using the command:

```
(megara) $ python -m megaradrp.visualization test/index.fits \
-c 0 --min-cut 0.8 --max-cut 1.2
```


Figure 24: Ratio between the `mean_1000_2000.fits` and `mean_2000_3000.fits` images generated with `megaratoools-rss_arith`.

Note that the spectral range explored by this spectral-index image is rather small, which leads to a very small dynamic range. Nevertheless, most of the spaxels showing bright emission from the source reveal a relatively blue color as expected for the spectral type of this spectrophotometric standard star.

The user should be also aware when using this tool that any operation involving a logarithmic or intensity ratios might lead to some warnings. These tools should properly handle (and create when necessary) NaN values but we cannot guarantee that any other software to be run on these products will have no issues using these data.

We note that `megaratoools-rss_arith` can be also used on extracted (1D) spectra created with the `megaratoools-extract_spectrum` tool described in Section 6.3. The instruction to use it on extracted spectra would be something like the following:

```
(megara) $ megaratoools-rss_arith test/list_1D \
-e '2.0*ima1+ima2' -o test/output_1D.fits
```

where `list_1D` should be a text ascii file with the (in this case, two) extracted spectra on which the numerical operation is to be performed (similar to the `test/images.txt` file quoted above for RSS files) and `output_1D.fits` would be the output 1D spectrum. This output file is fully compatible with our `megaratoools-plot_spectrum` or `megaratoools-analyze_spectrum` tools.

7.11 Megaratoools-hypercube

Some observations with the MEGARA LCB might require of acquiring multiple points to mosaic an extended astrophysical object. In order to combine the information from all the different RSS files generated by the DRP from each of the individual observations we have developed a code based on the `megaradrp-cube` tool but that is able to handle a series of RSS files placed at different adjacent positions in the sky combined them all together to create a single large cube. This tool is called `megaratoools-hypercube` and its online help can be obtained by doing:

```
(megara) $ megaratoools-hypercube -h
usage: convert_rss_cube [-h] [-l] [-c] [-p PIXEL_SIZE] [-o OUTFILE] [-d]
                        [-m {nn,linear}] [--wcs-pa-from-header] [-trim] [-hyp]
```

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```

                [-helio] [-trimm [TRIMMING_NUMBERS ...]]
                rss

positional arguments:
  rss                RSS file / List of RSS files

options:
  -h, --help          show this help message and exit
  -l, --is-a-list     Use for -s being a list of FITS spectra
  -c, --is-a-cube    Use for -s being a list of cubes (not rss) spectra
  -p PIXEL_SIZE, --pixel-size PIXEL_SIZE
                    Pixel size in arc seconds (default = 0.4)
  -o OUTFILE, --outfile OUTFILE
                    Name of the output cube file (default = test)
  -d, --disable-scaling
                    Disable flux conservation
  -m {nn,linear}, --method {nn,linear}
                    Method of interpolation
  --wcs-pa-from-header
                    Use PA angle from header
  -trim, --trimming   Use for trimming the cubes
  -hyp, --hyper       Use for creating the hypercube
  -helio, --helio     Use for applying heliocentric velocity correction
  -trimm [TRIMMING_NUMBERS ...], --trimming-numbers [TRIMMING_NUMBERS ...]
                    Use for declare the number of rows and columns you
                    want to trim. [Bottom rows, top rows, left column,
                    right column] (default= 1,2,1,1)

```

Although this tool determines the position on the sky based on the image WCS solution, it also allows to apply additional RA & Dec offsets to each of the individual generated cube sections (one from input RSS frame). Besides, one can also shift and scale the flux levels of each of the cube sections to take into account possible non-photometric conditions during the observation. These corrections are introduced as part of the input file where the list of RSS images to combine are included. An example of such a file is given below:

```

(megara) $ cat test/list_hypercube
test/reduced_rss_OB0001_B.fits 0.0 0.0 0.0 1.0
test/reduced_rss_OB0002_B.fits 0.0 0.0 0.0 1.0
test/reduced_rss_OB0003_B.fits 0.0 0.0 0.0 1.0
test/reduced_rss_OB0004_B.fits 0.0 0.0 0.0 1.0

```

The first column is the RSS filename, columns 2 and 3 correspond to the offsets (in arcsec) of the different pointings, column 4 allows to introduce offsets to the flux levels measured in the corresponding pointing and column 5 is the scaling factor to be applied to the flux of each pointing. The example listed above would be the one to be used if the astrometry and flux calibration of all RSS files is perfect.

An example of how the tool should be run would be the following:

```

(megara) $ megaratools-hypercube test/list_hypercube \
        -l -o test/cube.fits -p 0.4 -m linear --wcs-pa-from-header -trim -hyp -helio

```

In this case the pixel size of the `cube.fits` output file would be 0.4 arcsec/pixel, the cube would be generated using linear interpolation, 2 two rows and 1 bottom row, 1 left and right columns would be removed from each cube before they are combined together. The best number of rows and columns to be removed depends on the pixel size, so it can be modified by using the `-trimm` option. Besides, `megaradrp-tools_hypercube` allows to put all (topocentric) wavelength calibrations to a common barycenter wavelength calibration.

The use can also use this tool to simply generate a list of cubes from individual RSS files by removing the `-hyp` option.

KNOWN ISSUES

8.1 Matplotlib 3 in Mac OS X

In the case of using matplotlib 3 under Mac OS X (installations starting in 2019), in order to avoid a potential error associated to the use of the `libc++abi.dylib` library by the TkAgg backend, we recommend you to add the following line to the `$HOME/.matplotlib/matplotlibrc` file (you should create the file if this does not exist):

```
(megara) $ more $HOME/.matplotlib/matplotlibrc
backend: TkAgg
```

Note that TkAgg is the default backend in Mac OS X. If you want to use alternative ones they also need to be installed, or course.

8.2 Compiling in Mac OS X 10.10 or later

Should the user be interested in compiling part of the software on their own, we note that in the case of the distribution of Mac OS X 10.10 or later they should include the following environment variable in the `$HOME/.bashrc` shell configuration file:

```
(megara) $ more $HOME/.bashrc
export MACOSX_DEPLOYMENT_TARGET=10.9
```

8.3 Bash shell

Bash shell is the default shell for using the MEGARA DRP and the **megara-tools**. Please, be aware that starting on Mac OS X 10.15 “Catalina” the default shell is zsh. Tests on zsh have not yet been performed to ensure its compatibility MEGARA DRP and **megara-tools**.

ACRONYMS

ADC	Analog-Digital Converter / Conversion
AIV	Assembly, Integration and Verification
BPM	Bad-Pixels Mask
CCD	Charged-Coupled Device
DRP	Data Reduction Pipeline
DU	Digital Unit
FC	Folded-Cassegrain
FMAT	Fiber-MOS Assignment Tool
FWHM	Full-Width at Half-Maximum
GTC	Gran Telescopio CANARIAS
ICM	Instrument Calibration Module
IFU	Integral Field Unit
IFS	Integral Field Spectrograph / Integral Field Spectroscopy
IPA	Instrument Position Angle
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LCB	Large Compact Bundle

LICA

Laboratorio de Instrumentación Científica Avanzada

MEGARA

Multi-Espectrógrafo en GTC de Alta Resolución para Astronomía

MOS

Multi-Object Spectrograph / Multi-Object Spectroscopy

PA

Position Angle

PDF

Portable Document Format

RoN

Readout Noise

RSS

Row-Stacked Spectrum

ROTANG

Folded-Cassegrain Rotator Angle

UCM

Universidad Complutense de Madrid

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